

EHDEN

EUROPEAN HEALTH DATA & EVIDENCE NETWORK

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European Health Data & Evidence Network

WP2 – Outcome Driven Healthcare

D2.3 OMOP-CDM enhancements for outcome driven healthcare

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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the EHDEN Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

EMC	Erasmus Universitair Medisch Centrum Rotterdam- The Netherlands (Project Coordinator)
Synapse	Synapse Research Management Partners S.L. - Spain
UOXF	The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Oxford - United Kingdom
UTARTU	Tartu Ulikool - Estonia
UAVR	Universidade de Aveiro – Portugal
The Hyve	The Hyve BV – the Netherlands
Odysseus	Odysseus Data Services SRO – Czech Republic
EPF	Forum Europeen des Patients (FPE) - Luxembourg
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence – United Kingdom
UMC	Stiftelsen WHO Collaborating Centre for International Drug Monitoring - Sweden
ICHOM	International Consortium for Health Outcomes measurement LTD - United Kingdom
Janssen	Janssen Pharmaceutica NV – Belgium (Project Lead)
Pfizer	Pfizer Limited – United Kingdom
Abbvie	AbbVie Inc - United States
IRIS	Institut De Recherches Internationales Servier - France
SARD	Sanofi Aventis Recherche & Developpement - France
Bayer	Bayer Aktiengesellschaft - Germany
Lilly	Eli Lilly and Company Limited – United Kingdom
AZ	AstraZeneca AB - Sweden
Novartis	Novartis Pharma AG - Switzerland
UCB	UCB Biopharma SPRL - Belgium
Celgene	Celgene Management SARL - Switzerland

Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IMI JU for the undertaking of the EHDEN project (806968).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The EHDEN Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst EHDEN participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.
ICHOM	ICHOM (International Consortium for Health Outcomes Measurement, www.ichom.org) is a not-for-profit organization founded in 2012 that aims to unlock the potential of value-based healthcare by defining global Standard Sets of outcome measures and driving adoption and reporting of these measures worldwide.
Standard Set	An ICHOM Standard Set encompasses standardized outcomes, measurement tools, time points and risk adjustment factors for a given condition. ICHOM standard sets are developed through consensus and the process involves

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PROM – **Patient**
Report **Outcome**
measure

experts and patient representatives, to ensure the standard sets include those outcomes most relevant to patients. Currently, 28 standard sets are available.

Patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs) are instruments, usually questionnaires, measuring the patients' views of their health status

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

Introduction: EHDEN’s mission is to develop a federated research data network, standardized to OMOP Common Data Model (OMOP-CDM). Work Package 2 has the objective to enable the transition towards outcomes-driven healthcare systems in Europe. As part of this work, WP2 intends to extend the OMOP-CDM with the ICHOM standard sets. WP2 Deliverable 2.3 (D2.3) assesses the potential marriage of ICHOM’s standard sets and the EHDEN/OHDSI technology stack, in particular the OMOP-CDM.

Aims & Objectives: D2.3 aims to facilitate the extension of the OMOP-CDM to include ICHOM specific data domains such as patient reported outcome data. D2.3 will use the prioritised standard sets as proof of concepts to identify gaps in the OMOP-CDM structures and vocabularies and propose how this can be generalised to all standard sets. This aim has been refined to the following three main objectives.

1. Identify gaps in the mapping of the Inflammatory Arthritis and Prostate Cancer standard sets to the OMOP-CDM **structures**.
2. Identify gaps in the mapping of these standard sets to the OMOP-CDM **vocabulary**
3. Based on gaps identified in objectives above, propose future activities to fill those gaps.

Method: This research was exploratory in nature and the method drew from several sources. Central was the Book of OHDSI, ICHOM Reference guides, EHDEN Deliverable 3.2, EHDEN Study-a-thon outputs, and other previous publications. The steps can be summarised as: data acquisition, mapping ICHOM’s prioritised standard sets to the OMOP-CDM, generalisation of the techniques, further investigation using the OHDSI data analytics tools, and reflection on how to better align the two standards.

Results & Outputs: The key findings are:

- The OMOP-CDM **structure** can currently accommodate the datatypes, the question & answer types, and the recommended patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs) from the ICHOM Inflammatory Arthritis and Prostate Cancer standard sets.
- The OMOP-CDM **standard vocabularies** currently have patchy coverage of the vocabulary required to accommodate the prioritised standard sets and PROMs. This coverage can be enhanced at a local level by creating new vocabulary entries **and/or** by requesting that they required entries are included by default in new releases of the standard vocabulary.

The key outputs are:

- Matching/Mapping of ICHOM prioritised standard set to the OMOP-CDM and gap identification (See Appendices B&C).
- Generalised approaches for matching/mapping ICHOM standard sets to the OMOP-CDM structure and vocabulary including classification of question-types in the standard sets.
- Example approach for inserting ICHOM standard dataset into OMOP-CDM.
- Recommendations for stakeholders to enable and enhance the process.

Discussion/Conclusion:

- Mapping the prioritised standard sets to the CDM structures worked well – including the accommodation of timing logic & care-pathways. However, it is likely that other standard sets and real-world applications will bring new issues to light.
- Coverage of the prioritised standard sets in the CDM standard vocabularies was found to be patchy and this is likely to be an ongoing issue with real-world datasets (RWD). The vocabulary enhancement process needs consideration. Should commonly used PROMs be in the standard

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vocabularies? Should the mappings primarily aim to accommodate benchmarking, or should the mappings support the deeper EHDEN-adopted ‘FAIR’ philosophy?

- Mastering the OHDSI/EHDEN/ICHOM environments proved a steep learning curve for the researchers - in both in the extract-transform-load (ETL) phase and in the data analytics phase. Many of the sophisticated tools and artefacts are open-source, intricate, and are new or untested in some respects. Data partners will need planning and implementation support. Guidelines are needed for implementation of standard sets in EHDEN and benchmarking. Lines of communication need to be established between ICHOM, OHDSI, the vocabulary teams, and data partners to facilitate efficient resolution of queries and issues.
- The discoveries from this exercise will be enriched by application to RWD although this will bring its own unique issues, particularly on data quality and provenance.

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1. INTRODUCTION

EHDEN’s mission is to develop a federated data network, standardized to the OMOP common data model (OMOP-CDM) and it aspires to be the trusted observational research ecosystem to enable better health decisions, outcomes and care. EHDEN works in collaboration with OHDSI, uses and participates in the development of OHDSI’s data analytics toolset and incorporates ICHOM’s health outcomes standard sets. The core of EHDEN is the use of the OMOP-CDM, standardised outcome assessment (ICHOM), and transparent, open-source analytics (OHDSI). (ehden.eu)

OHDSI focusses on generating reliable evidence from real-world data, answering three types of questions: Characterisation, population-level estimation (PLE), and patient-level prediction (PLP). Characterisation answers questions about a dataset, the persons in the dataset, the persons in a cohort and how these answers can vary. PLE can support causal inferences about the effects of healthcare interventions like: What are the causal effects of a medication? Which treatment works better? What is the risk of an adverse event as a result of an intervention? Patient level prediction tries to answer the question: What will happen to a specific patient? (ohdsi.org)

ICHOM’s mission is to realise value-based healthcare by defining global standard sets of outcome measures representing the results people care about most when seeking treatment, including functional improvement and the ability to live normal, productive lives. ICHOM drives the adoption and reporting of these measures worldwide, with the objective of achieving standardized outcomes, benchmarking between institutions facilitating system improvement (ichom.org).

EHDEN’s Work Package 2 (WP2) has as its main objective - enabling the transition towards outcomes-driven healthcare systems in Europe. This WP will provide the basis for ensuring that the EHDEN framework is usable in the regulatory, HTA, and payer contexts. In addition, the WP aims to assess whether the OMOP-CDM can accommodate the ICHOM standard sets.

EHDEN’s D2.3 starts to resolve these aims and objectives into practical exercises, exploring their feasibility in the EHDEN project, examining the use of the OMOP-CDM to accommodate ICHOM’s standard sets through an extract-transform-load (ETL) process, exploring how outcome driven healthcare questions can be answered, and exposing hurdles encountered.

2. BACKGROUND & GROUNDING LITERATURE

Deliverable 2.1 prioritised inflammatory arthritis (IA) and prostate cancer (localised and advanced) as the ICHOM standard sets to be used in subsequent deliverables and proofs of concept. These were selected by EHDEN consortium members using the following considerations:

- Can the standard set be used as part of EHDEN research activities that are either ongoing or planned for years 1 and 2 of the project?
- Which conditions are indicated as high priority through a ranking exercise?
- Which standard sets overlap with current or future BD4BO projects?

2.1 ICHOM’s Inflammatory Arthritis Standard Set (IASS)

ICHOM’s IASS incorporates four conditions: Rheumatoid Arthritis, Psoriatic Arthritis, Ankylosing Spondylitis, and Juvenile Idiopathic Arthritis. The IASS covers all treatment options but does not enumerate them. Supporting ICHOM documentation lists some potential treatments in two groups: Pharmacological (NSAIDs¹, Glucocorticoids, Biologic DMARDS², Non-biologic DMARDS, DMARDS) and

¹ Non-Steroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drugs

² Disease Modifying Anti-Rheumatic Drugs

Non-pharmacological treatments (Surgical and Other). The IASS groups outcomes as Patient-reported (Pain, Fatigue, Activity limitation etc) and Treatment-Specific or Clinician-reported (Serious adverse events, Response/remission, and Inflammatory disease activity).

Inclusion of risk factors or case-mix variables allows risk adjustment to reach the goal of enabling meaningful global comparisons. The IASS groups these variables as: Demographic factors (Age, Sex, Education level), Behavioural (Smoking), and Baseline Clinical Status (Comorbidities, Physician-reported IA diagnosis, Disease duration, Immunological).

Figure 1: Inflammatory Arthritis Model: Initial Conditions + Treatments leading to Outcomes

The IASS also includes a timeline for collection of the data collection represented in Figure 2 below.

Follow-Up Timeline and Sample Questionnaires

The following timeline illustrates when Standard Set variables should be collected from patients, clinicians, and administrative sources. Links to the sample questionnaires may be found in the legend below.

Figure 2: IASS data collection timeline (from IASS Reference Guide)

For a full explanation of ICHOM’s Inflammatory Arthritis Standard Set please refer to the reference guide available at <https://ichom.org/files/medical-conditions/inflammatory-arthritis/inflammatory-arthritis-reference-guide.pdf>

2.2 ICHOM’s Localised Prostate Cancer Standard Set (LPCSS)

ICHOM’s LPCSS specifies the following treatment options: Active Surveillance, Watchful Waiting, Radical Prostatectomy, External Beam Radiation Therapy, Androgen Deprivation Therapy, Focal Therapy, and Other. The LPCSS groups outcomes as Acute complications of treatment (major surgical complications, major radiation complications), Patient-reported health status (Urinary continence, Urinary frequency, Bowel irritation, Hormonal symptoms, sexual dysfunction) and Survival and disease control (Overall survival, cause-specific survival, development of metastasis, biochemical recurrence).

Inclusion of risk factors or case-mix variables allows risk adjustment to reach the goal of enabling meaningful global comparisons. The LPCSS groups these variables as: Patient factors (Age, Comorbidities), Baseline tumour factors, Pathological information, Treatment variables.

Figure 3: Localised Prostate Cancer: Initial Conditions + Treatments leading to Outcomes

The LPCSS also includes a timeline for collection of the data collection represented in Figure 4 below.

Follow-Up Timeline and Sample Questionnaires

The following timeline illustrates when Standard Set variables should be collected from patients, clinicians, and administrative sources. Links to the sample questionnaires may be found in the legend below.

Figure 4: Sample LPCSS data collection timeline (from LPCSS Reference Guide)

For a full explanation of ICHOM’s Localised Prostate Cancer Standard Set please refer to the reference guide available at <https://ichom.org/files/medical-conditions/localized-prostate-cancer/localized-prostate-cancer-reference-guide.pdf>

2.3 ICHOM’s Advanced Prostate Cancer Standard Set (APCSS)

ICHOM’s APCSS follows a similar format summarised below:

Figure 5: Advanced Prostate Cancer: Initial Conditions + Treatments leading to Outcomes

The APCSS also includes a timeline for collection of the data collection represented in **Figure 6** below.

Figure 6: Sample APCSS data collection timeline (from APCSS Reference Guide)

For a full explanation of ICHOM’s Advanced Prostate Cancer Standard Set please refer to the reference guide available at <https://ichom.org/files/medical-conditions/advanced-prostate-cancer/advanced-prostate-cancer-reference-guide.pdf>

2.4 The OMOP-CDM background

The OMOP-CDM V6 is represented in Figure 7 below, with each shaded section containing a group of closely related tables e.g. the standardised clinical data section contains data about patients stored at the individual patient level. The standardised vocabularies section contains the available vocabularies (e.g. SNOMED & LOINC) in a stacked-up table named CONCEPT, and their principal relationships to each other in CONCEPT_RELATIONSHIP and CONCEPT_ANCESTOR.

Figure 7: OMOP-CDM V6

The key tables for assessing the OMOP-CDM’s structural suitability to facilitate ICHOM’s standard sets are: PERSON, OBSERVATION, CONCEPT, and SURVEY_CONDUCT. Other tables also play supporting roles: MEASUREMENT, CONDITION_OCCURRENCE, PROCEDURE_OCCURRENCE, DRUG_EXPOSURE, CONCEPT_RELATIONSHIP, CONCEPT_ANCESTOR, FACT_RELATIONSHIP & SOURCE_TO_CONCEPT_MAP. Details on all of the tables can be found here³.

- PERSON contains records uniquely identifying each patient in the source data who is “time at-risk” to have clinical observations recorded within the source systems.
- OBSERVATION table captures clinical facts about a Person obtained in the context of examination, questioning or a procedure. Data not represented by any other domains, such as social and lifestyle facts, medical history, family history, etc. are recorded here.
- CONCEPT holds the standard vocabularies.
- SURVEY_CONDUCT is responsible for the administration of surveys & questionnaires and contains one record each uniquely identifying a survey instance.
- MEASUREMENT table contains records on measurements, i.e. structured values (numerical or categorical) obtained through systematic and standardized examination or testing of a person or person's sample.
- CONDITION_OCCURRENCE records a person’s conditions suggesting the presence of a disease or medical condition which can be stated as a diagnosis, a sign, or a symptom, either observed by a provider or reported by the patient.
- PROCEDURE_OCCURRENCE table records activities or processes ordered by, or carried out by, a healthcare provider on the patient with a diagnostic or therapeutic purpose.
- DRUG_EXPOSURE entries are inferred from clinical events such as prescriptions, pharmacy dispensing, EHR entries, and patient reported events.
- The key table in the standardised vocabulary is the CONCEPT table with further relationships defined in the CONCEPT_RELATIONSHIP and CONCEPT_ANCESTOR, FACT_RELATIONSHIPS, and SOURCE_TO_CONCEPT_MAP tables. This work is initiated by the OHDSI Vocabulary team and results in a downloadable, single catalogue of medical terms. OHDSI’s philosophy is that

³ <https://github.com/OHDSI/CommonDataModel/wiki>

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a CONCEPT_ID has the same meaning for all researchers using the CDM thus facilitating networked research.

Standardising data to the OMOP structure and vocabularies will help establish semantic connections between ICHOM's standard sets and medical coding systems such as SNOMED AND LOINC.

3. AIMS & OBJECTIVES

Task 2.2 is 'Extend the OMOP-CDM and vocabularies to include ICHOM standard Sets'

"The ICHOM condition specific standard sets need to be defined using OMOP terminology to enable the marriage between these two standards to take place. This foundational work will be prioritized by the conditions agreed in task 2.1 and will define the framework for all ICHOM standard sets. Building on this model, the OMOP-CDM will be extended to include ICHOM specific data domains that are not adequately defined in the current data model such as "patient reported outcome (PRO)" data. Both the logical and physical data models need to be extended along with the vocabularies used to define the data. The OHDSI OMOP standard vocabularies will be extended to include ICHOM-specific benchmark data and PRO instrument data. ICHOM, Odysseus and EMC will work closely together to accommodate all current ICHOM standard sets and enable integration of future patient-reported outcomes."

Deliverable 2.1 prioritised three ICHOM Standard Sets, Inflammatory Arthritis, Localised and Advanced Prostate Cancer as the areas of interest for proof-of-concept exercises [Available here](#).

Deliverable 2.2 initiated examination of the current coverage of these standard sets in the OMOP-CDM model and in the standard vocabularies, where preliminary mappings of the prioritized ICHOM standard sets, Inflammatory Arthritis and Prostate Cancer were created [Available here](#).

Deliverable 2.2 proposed a twofold approach for the next steps in WP2 Outcome Driven Healthcare:

1. *Review and work out the suggested concept mappings for data items in the prioritized standard sets, establishing mappings of the data items in the ICHOM standard sets onto OMOP standard concepts in a manner that aligns with current convention and best practices of the OHDSI vocabulary team.*
2. *Explore and establish good practices for supporting the ICHOM use case by trying out the translated OMOP data items in combination with concept sets, cohort definitions, cohort pathways and other phenotypes designed to capture the business logic underlying ICHOM standard sets in a generic, re-useable manner.*

D2.3 aims to facilitate the extension of the OMOP-CDM to include ICHOM specific data domains such as patient reported outcome data. This deliverable will use the prioritised standard sets as proof of concepts to identify gaps in the OMOP-CDM structures and vocabularies and propose how this can be effectively generalised to all standard sets.

This has been refined to the following three main objectives achieving the above aim.

1. Identify gaps in the mapping of the Inflammatory Arthritis and Prostate Cancer standard sets to the OMOP-CDM structures.
2. Identify gaps in the mapping of the Inflammatory Arthritis and Prostate Cancer standard Set to the OMOP-CDM vocabularies.
3. Based on gaps identified in objectives above, propose future activities to fill those gaps, and to open the possibility of future collaboration with EHDEN.

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4. METHOD SUMMARY

This research was exploratory in nature and the method outlined below drew from several sources. Central was the Book of OHDSI⁴, EHDEN Deliverable 3.2⁵, ICHOM Reference Guides⁶, EHDEN Study-athon outputs^{7 8} and previous publications. The steps to achieve the objectives can be summarised as:

- Get Data
- Convert data for IASS and LPCSS to OMOP-CDM (ETL)
 - Generalise the method for application to other standard sets
 - Apply the method to the Advanced Prostate Cancer standard set
- Data Analytics Design
 - Preliminary Analysis Decisions
 - Analysis Strategy
 - Analysis Implementation
 - Architecture and Deployment
 - Define research questions (RQs)
- Data Analytics Execution (Using Atlas)
 - Define Concept Sets
 - Define Cohorts/Study Population
 - Review Data/DQ
 - Create & Run Study Package if feasible
- Final report on the above

5. EXECUTION OF THE METHOD & RESULTS

5.1 Get data

The use of both real-world data (RWD) and synthetic data were considered. Synthetic data has many advantages for exploratory, testing, and educational purposes. Its creation is more efficient and quicker than accessing RWD in many cases. Synthetic data can also offer advantages allowing testing for variables not always present in RWD e.g. the generation of the data could be customised to represent various age-groups etc. Synthetic data is not personal data and accordingly, not subject to data protection legislation and limited ethics requirements. However, synthetic data also has shortcomings e.g. it may miss some random behaviours and not be truly representative.

In this case, data was generated using Synthea for pragmatic reasons – primarily the lack of immediate access to RWD and the inevitable delay that would result from sourcing such patient-level data and from clearing the associated ethics & data protection hurdles. Ultimately, the proposals in this work need to be battle-tested with real-world data.

⁴ <https://ohdsi.github.io/TheBookOfOhdsi/>

⁵

https://synapsemanagers.sharepoint.com/sites/EHDEN/Shared%20Documents/Deliverables/Submitted%20deliverables/IMI2_EHDEN_D3.2_First%20Report%20Pipeline_v1.0.pdf

⁶ <https://ichom.org/files/medical-conditions/inflammatory-arthritis/inflammatory-arthritis-reference-guide.pdf>

⁷ https://github.com/ohdsi-studies/EhdenRaPrediction/blob/master/documents/RA_PLP_protocol_27012020.docx

⁸ <https://github.com/ohdsi-studies/TofacitinibSafetyinRA/blob/master/Overall%20Documentation/OHDSI%20F2F%20protocol%20v2.2.docx>

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The Synthea™ synthetic data generator⁹ is an open-source, synthetic patient generator that models the medical history of synthetic patients. It created realistic patient data and associated health records. The resulting data was free of privacy, and security restrictions. The generation process could be customised to meet differing needs including demographics. Populations could also be generated reflecting differing disease groups including rheumatoid arthritis (RA) using drop-in modules. However, this functionality did not deliver any obvious benefits to this work. In fact, the general dataset had a number of PROM-like observations such as pain scores, but these were not present in the RA dataset. Accordingly, a general population of 100k¹⁰ patients was created using Synthea. This data contained much of the demographic, diagnosis and treatment data including 338 patients with recorded a condition of rheumatoid arthritis. A synthetically generated dataset (Synpuf) was also available in the test-Atlas environment but had no significant arthritis population.

Figure 8: ETL process

Supplemental data was necessary to represent the ICHOM specifics such as survey responses and PROM data elements and this was executed manually. Both data arms were then subjected to an ETL process before insertion into the OMOP-CDM instance. The Synthea-OMOP ETL¹¹ process was not trivial and required customisation. This exercise focussed primarily on the ICHOM specific ETL issues.

There are other low-level interventions possible within Synthea to manipulate the dataset generation and increase the number of IA type events. Specifically, there is a facility to add a drop-in module for IA or to manipulate the characteristics of a generated population. This may merit further investigation if researchers need specific populations. Also, custom code could have been written simulating specific data elements in the final OMOP-CDM to achieve the same goal.

There are other low-level interventions possible within Synthea to manipulate the dataset generation and increase the number of IA type events. Specifically, there is a facility to add a drop-in module for IA or to manipulate the characteristics of a generated population. This may merit further investigation if researchers need specific populations. Also, custom code could have been written simulating specific data elements in the final OMOP-CDM to achieve the same goal.

5.2 Convert data for IASS and LPCSS to OMOP-CDM (ETL)

In an ideal scenario, source data is perfect, semantically equivalent to, and seamlessly and completely converted to the OMOP-CDM. The conversion would preserve ICHOM's standard sets' semantics and ICHOM's care-pathway and temporal logic. The real world is different. The source data is rarely perfect and data conversion is not a perfect process. There may be tables and fields in the source data that have no equivalent in the OMOP-CDM and vice-versa. Also, the contents of some of the fields in the source data may have no appropriately matching entry in the standard vocabulary. Data quality also needs consideration. Is there missing, incorrect, or irrelevant data?

In summary, there may be 'types' of data in the source data that have no equivalent in the OMOP-CDM and there may be specific instances of data that do not map to an entry in the standard vocabulary and there may be consequences to loss of data. Achieving semantic equivalence at the entity, attribute, and instance are the ideal goals.

The conversion of a dataset into the OMOP-CDM is a process known as extract-transform-load (ETL). The next sections detail the approaches taken to the ETL process. For this deliverable, there are two arms to the ETL process: the Synthea data ETL and ICHOM specific ETL as in Figure 9. The combination of both arms will result in an OMOP-CDM instance with patients and ICHOM survey data.

⁹ <https://synthetichealth.github.io/synthea/>

¹⁰ Generation on desktop PC (Intel Core i7 @2.40 GHz, 16GB RAM) took 2 hours plus 2 hours to ETL

¹¹ <https://github.com/OHDSI/ETL-Synthea>

Figure 9: Expanded ETL process

5.2.1 Arm 1: Synthea data

The Synthea-OMOP ETL module initially did not work as planned. As there were others in WP2 working on this, waiting for their solution seemed the sensible approach. In the interim, the ETL processes for RWD was followed as far as possible (see Figure 21 and Figure 22) This had value as this is the path that will generally be taken by RWD partners. Converting the ETL document generated by Rabbit-in-a-hat was not pursued as this was a significant programming task beyond scope.

No external solution to converting the Synthea generated data was forthcoming in the time required, and the Synthea-OMOP ETL module was revisited with a programming hat on. The source code was downloaded, the errors followed as they were generated and solved to the point where the ETL runs almost to completion. All the key data converted.

5.2.2 Arm 2 : ICHOM survey data

The ICHOM ETL arm is where the gaps between the prioritised standard sets and the OMOP-CDM are identified and is the key part of this investigation.

It is likely that data elements in the standard set data dictionary (SSDD) or the source data itself do not match well with the standardized vocabulary model and contents. In this case, custom CONCEPT_IDS can be added to the list of OHDSI-provided concepts. These additional concepts must be present for all subsequent analysis of the dataset.

When deciding how to map the data to standard concepts, the strategic aims of the conversion to OMOP-CDM need to be considered. The simple approach is to define new standard concepts for each of the standard set data elements. All of the new concepts can be assigned to the domain 'observation' and they are then stored in the OBSERVATION table. This ETL process can be relatively straightforward, however, the data in this format may be difficult or impossible for other researchers to find as it may not be where it is expected i.e. it does not follow ETL conventions. To facilitate remote network research, the data elements should be matched or mapped to the existing standard concepts as much as possible. Following this, the data will ultimately be 'assigned' to the appropriate event table and may be one of OBSERVATION, MEASUREMENT, PROCEDURE_OCCURRENCE, CONDITION_OCCURRENCE, DRUG_EXPOSURE. The next sections of this report document the approach taken to assessing the prioritised standard sets following Arm 2 of Figure 9.

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ETL of The Inflammatory Arthritis Standard Set (IASS)

The IASS is described by two ICHOM documents: The Inflammatory Arthritis Reference Guide¹² and the data dictionary¹³ (IADD). The reference guide outlines the philosophy behind the standard sets development. The IADD defines the data elements including data types and conventions for usage.

Objective 1: Identify gaps in the mapping of the IASS to the OMOP-CDM structures

In this section the data types in the SSDD, the data elements in the SSDD, data types and elements in the recommended PROMs will be examined. The OMOP-CDM itself is platform independent with data types defined generically using ANSI SQL data types (VARCHAR, INTEGER, FLOAT, DATE, DATETIME, CLOB)¹⁴.

What datatypes are in the IASS?

The datatypes in the prioritised standard sets can be generally categorised as:

1. Numeric responses e.g. IDs, Year of Birth, 0/1, Numerical rating scales and converted values.
2. Dates.
3. Text responses e.g. Name of measurement, other free text.
4. Categorical (enumerated) responses e.g. Y/N, Gender, Education Level, Smoking Status, Likert type scales.

In addition to these data types, the PROMS questions in the IASS are typically one of the following:

1. Scaled responses e.g. Likert scale. These are typically expressed on a numerical scale (0-5) in the SSDD.
2. Multiple responses e.g. I use 'Cane', 'Crutches' & 'Wheelchair'.

These datatypes can all be accommodated in the OMOP-CDM. It is important to note that there are potentially other types of questions not encountered in the prioritised standard sets and may not be easily accommodated such as data-reference questions or imager choosers¹⁵.

An exception exists in the IADD in the IA_DIAG data element which allows for multiple diagnoses of different IA diseases to be stored in one field. This technique is error-prone, difficult to implement and computationally inefficient.

What types of questions are in the IASS?

The data elements of the prioritised standard sets were assessed and can be grouped into a small number of variations based on how they can be accommodated in the OMOP-CDM. These variations are documented in the following types for convenience:

Type 0: Perfect match:

¹² <https://ichom.org/files/medical-conditions/inflammatory-arthritis/inflammatory-arthritis-reference-guide.pdf>

¹³ https://connect.ichom.org/resource_type/data-dictionary/

¹⁴ [https://ohdsi.github.io/TheBookOfOhdsi/\(P.34\)](https://ohdsi.github.io/TheBookOfOhdsi/(P.34))

¹⁵ <https://www.questionpro.com/article/survey-question-answer-type.html>

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There is a table-field (entity-attribute) matching the SSDD element. E.g. date-of-birth

Type 1: Possible multiple answers to a single question:

To accommodate this type of question, list the question/answer combinations and create new standard concepts for each of them. E.g. Was ‘*Watchful Waiting*’ a treatment modality? Was ‘*Active Surveillance*’ a treatment modality? Has your doctor told you that you have *high blood pressure*? etc.

To ensure that the data is ‘findable’ and available for network research, a corresponding entry in the condition, measurement, or procedure tables should be considered.

Type 2: Date of an event:

There are several approaches to this type of data element¹⁶. In the case of dates relating to a condition, date-of-onset and date-of-diagnosis must be distinguished. Date-of-diagnosis will conventionally be stored with the diagnosis in the CONDITION table. Date-of-onset (4181873) can be stored in the OBSERVATION table with a link to the diagnosis through the FACT_RELATIONSHIP table. However, use of this method is seen as problematic for network research. Alternatively, the OMOP-CDM V6 allows linking of an entry in the OBSERVATION table to an event through the OBSERVATION_EVENT_ID and OBSERVATION_EVENT_CONCEPT_ID fields. It is also suggested that the data speaks for itself i.e. the date-of-onset should always be same as the earliest date-of-diagnosis recorded.

To accommodate this type of question, map to a matching standard concept if available e.g. ‘Date of histological diagnosis’ may map to SNOMED concept 373800009 ‘Cancer diagnosis based on primary site histological evidence’. If no match, create a new standard concept, in this case, ‘Date of histological diagnosis’. Several other ‘dates of diagnosis’ in the standard vocabulary have a domain of ‘Observation’, whereas cancer diagnoses tend to have a domain of ‘Condition’. If there is an associated entry in an event table (PROCEDURE OR CONDITION_OCCURRENCE) then use one of the methods above to link to the date.

Type 3: Free text entry:

Map to a matching standard concept if available. Otherwise, create a new standard concept e.g. ‘Type of focal therapy’ typically as an ‘Observation’. In this example, focal therapy is not in the standard vocabulary, but common types of this therapy are e.g. cryotherapy, laser ablation, photodynamic therapy. This is similar to **Type 1**. The data in this text field should also be mapped to the standard concepts if possible, i.e. map the types of focal therapy to their standard concepts.

Type 4: Numeric measurement:

Map to a matching standard concept if available. Otherwise, create a new standard concept e.g. Numerical value of PSA level in ng/mL. This would normally have a domain of ‘Measurement’.

Type 5: Numeric indicating a count

e.g. Numerical value of number of biopsy cores. Map to a matching standard concept if available with the domain of ‘Observation’ and Value_as_Number holding the data.

Type 6: Numeric indicating a category

e.g. Clinical tumour stage. Map to a matching standard concept if available with the domain of ‘Observation’ and Value_as_Concept_ID containing the data. In this example, each of the clinical tumour stages has its own standard concept in the standard vocabularies. This appears to differ from Type 1 because, there is no reason to create a corresponding entry in an event table.

Type 7: Numeric indicating a category or number

¹⁶ <https://forums.ohdsi.org/t/how-to-store-date-of-onset-and-date-of-diagnosis-for-a-disease/9460/4>

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e.g. Gleason Score. Create a mapping to a matching standard concept if available with the domain of ‘Observation’ appearing correct and Value_as_Concept_ID containing the data. Each of the clinical Gleason scores has its own standard concept. It also appears feasible that the numeric value could be stored in the Value_as_Number field.

The IADD elements are divided into groups: Demographic factors, baseline characteristics, baseline condition factors, patient-reported health and wellbeing, and treatment-specific. These are dealt with in turn next. This builds on the work of Deliverable 2.2.

Demographic factors

The IASS demographic factors have straightforward mappings to the OMOP-CDM

Demographic Factors	IASS Data Dictionary	Location in OMOP-CDM
Age	Year of Birth Numeric	Type 0: PERSON.YEAR_OF_BIRTH
Sex	M/F/Unknown 1/2/999	Type 0: PERSON.GENDER_CONCEPT_ID
Education	International Standard Classification of Education (ISCE) 0/1/2/3	Type 6: If the ISCE is fully represented in the standard vocabulary, then OBSERVATION.CONCEPT_ID as ISCE concept and OBSERVATION.VALUE_AS_CONCEPT_ID representing ‘Primary’ etc. If grades of education not available, use numbers instead in VALUE_AS_NUMBER

Behavioural factors

The only IASS behavioural factor is smoking

Behavioural Factors	IASS Data Dictionary	OMOP-CDM
Smoking (assumed this is tobacco)	Never/Former/Current 0/1/2.	Type 6: OBSERVATION.VALUE_AS_NUMBER Or OBSERVATION.VALUE_AS_CONCEPT_ID ¹⁷

Baseline Clinical Status factors

The IASS Baseline Clinical Status factors have straightforward mappings to the OMOP-CDM

Baseline Clinical Status Factors	IASS Data Dictionary	OMOP-CDM
Comorbidities - Physician-reported	There are 11 Y/N questions recorded at baseline.	Type 1: OBSERVATION.VALUE_AS_CONCEPT_ID with the OBSERVATION_CONCEPT_ID being a custom question-answer pair and the answer being a Yes/No/Unknown CONCEPT_ID. If there is no definitive date associated with the comorbidity, the convention is to map it to e.g. ‘History of high blood pressure’
Physician-reported inflammatory arthritis diagnosis	RA, PA, AS, JIA 1,2,3,4. ¹⁸	Type 1: OBSERVATION.VALUE_AS_CONCEPT_ID with the OBSERVATION_CONCEPT_ID being a custom question-answer pair e.g. ‘Has your doctor every told you that you have <i>Rheumatoid Arthritis</i> ?’ and the answer being a Yes/No/Unknown CONCEPT_ID. Additionally - To ensure that the data is ‘findable’ and available for network research, a corresponding entry in the CONDITION_OCCURRENCE table for Rheumatoid Arthritis should be considered.
Disease Duration	Year of Diagnosis	Type 2: If an entry in the CONDITION_OCCURRENCE table exists, this value can be deduced from it.

¹⁷ A new smoking hierarchy is proposed for the OMOP-CDM <https://forums.ohdsi.org/t/proposal-for-new-smoking-conventions-please-weigh-in/9817>

¹⁸ It is unclear why multiple simultaneous diagnoses should be recorded in a single field in contrast to ‘Comorbidities’ where each observation has its own field. To facilitate the ETL, each potential diagnosis has its own field in a slightly modified dataset.

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		Otherwise, a matching question for each option in the previous data field is required. e.g. ‘What year did your doctor tell you that you had <i>Rheumatoid Arthritis</i> ?’
Immunological Rheumatoid factor	– Y/N/Unknown 0/1/999	Type 6: If element has a standard concept then map to it as OBSERVATION.OBSERVATION_CONCEPT_ID. Otherwise create a new standard concept. Store the answer value as OBSERVATION.VALUE_AS_NUMBER and/or OBSERVATION.VALUE_AS_CONCEPT_ID.
ACPA (presence-of)	Y/N/Unknown 0/1/999	As above.

Patient-reported health and wellbeing

Managing patient reported outcomes will be necessary if ICHOM’s standard sets are to be incorporated into the OMOP-CDM. Version 6 of the OMOP-CDM includes a table called SURVEY_CONDUCT designed to manage the data from surveys or questionnaires. Earlier versions of the OMOP-CDM did not have this table and need an alternative approach as introduced in Appendix F. In ICHOM terms, if these are patient reported surveys, then they would result in patient reported values or outcomes. While the current Atlas/WEBAPI release supports OMOP-CDM V5.3.x, it is planned to support V6 in Q3 2020¹⁹ and, given that the SURVEY_CONDUCT table closely matches the data requirements of patient reported questionnaires, it is pragmatic to utilise this. Earlier work also successfully accommodated survey type data without the SURVEY_CONDUCT table (See Appendix A). This is a brief description of how the SURVEY_CONDUCT table works.

The SURVEY_CONDUCT table in OMOP-CDM

The SURVEY_CONDUCT table contains the top-level information of an instance of a survey completed by a specific person i.e. for every survey completed by a person, there is one record in the SURVEY_CONDUCT table.

Each completed SURVEY has a unique SURVEY_ID. It also has a SURVEY_CONCEPT_ID linking it to a concept in the CONCEPT table identifying the survey e.g. EQ5D, VR12, SF12. Each survey should exist in the CONCEPT table. Each question on the survey should also exist in the CONCEPT table. Patient responses to survey questions are often stored in the OBSERVATION table²⁰. Each record in the OBSERVATION table represents a single question/response pair and is linked to a specific SURVEY/questionnaire using OBSERVATION.OBSERVATION_EVENT_ID and SURVEY_CONDUCT.SURVEY_CONDUCT_ID.

Each question on the survey in the OBSERVATION table has a related concept in the CONCEPT table linked from OBSERVATION.CONCEPT_EVENT_ID to CONCEPT.CONCEPT_ID. i.e. Each response record is the response to a specific question identified by the OBSERVATION_CONCEPT_ID.

The OBSERVATION table can also store survey scoring results. Many validated PRO questionnaires have scoring algorithms (many of which are proprietary) that return an overall patient score based on the answers provided. Survey scores are identified by their OBSERVATION_CONCEPT_ID and are linked back to the scored survey as above. Further details on the conventions and use of the SURVEY_CONDUCT table can be found here²¹.

¹⁹ <https://forums.ohdsi.org/t/webapi-and-atlas-with-cdm-v6/7956>

²⁰ It is also possible to store answers in the MEASUREMENT, PROCEDURE_OCCURRENCE, or CONDITION_OCCURRENCE, DRUG_EXPOSURE tables. This study focusses on the OBSERVATION table.

²¹ https://github.com/OHDSI/CommonDataModel/wiki/SURVEY_CONDUCT

Figure 10: SURVEY_CONDUCT relationships

Figure 2 showed the data collection timeline from the IASS Reference Guide requiring that data be collected at specific intervals. The SURVEY_CONDUCT table accommodates this ICHOM timing logic by naming the instance of the survey to reflect the survey timing e.g. ‘Baseline’ or ‘6 month follow up’ or by use of the TIMING_CONCEPT_ID or TIMING_SOURCE_VALUE fields in the SURVEY_CONDUCT table. This is one of the key advantages of the new table allowing the base name of the questionnaire to remain the same irrespective of its position in the care-pathway. This could be done using one of TIMING_CONCEPT_ID or TIMING_SOURCE_VALUE fields in the SURVEY_CONDUCT table. These relevant (structural) relationships are summarised in the entity relationship in Figure 10.

Treatment specific outcomes

The IASS treatment specific factors have are mapped as follows to the OMOP-CDM:

Demographic Factors	IASS Data Dictionary	OMOP-CDM
Serious Adverse Events	There are 7 Y/N questions recorded at baseline. Physician-reported.	Type 1: OBSERVATION.VALUE_AS_CONCEPT_ID with the OBSERVATION_CONCEPT_ID being a custom question-answer pair and the answer being a Yes/No CONCEPT_ID. Additionally - To ensure that the data is ‘findable’ and available for network research, a corresponding entry in the CONDITION_OCCURRENCE table for Rheumatoid Arthritis should be considered.
Response/Remission	Disease Activity Target 1 = Clinical remission 2 = Low disease activity, 3 = Both, 999 = Unknown	Type 6: If element has a standard concept then map to it as OBSERVATION.OBSERVATION_CONCEPT_ID. Otherwise create a new standard concept. Store the answer value as OBSERVATION.VALUE_AS_NUMBER and/or OBSERVATION.VALUE_AS_CONCEPT_ID.

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	Reached? (Y/N)	As above
Inflammatory Disease Activity	Which validated and internationally accepted composite score for inflammatory disease activity did you use?	Type 3: Free text entry Map to a matching standard concept if available. Otherwise, create a new standard concept.
	Result? Free text	Type 3: Free text entry OBSERVATION.VALUE_AS_STRING

Objective 2: Identify gaps in the mapping of the IASS to the OMOP-CDM vocabulary.

Many of the data elements in the SSDDs have matching standard concepts in the OMOP-CDM CONCEPT table. These can be browsed either using the ATLAS/ATHENA functionality or USAGI. For this work, USAGI is more useful as it also provides functionality creating a mapping file to allow the matching concepts to be imported into the OMOP-CDM instance.

From Figure 9

Steps:

- Prepare the IASS meta data for USAGI. First the data elements in the IASS were formatted to allow analysis and mapping in the USAGI application, by cutting and pasting the columns from the SS Data Dictionary Excel file into a new Excel workbook²².
- Start the USAGI application.
- Select menu item: File/Import Codes.
- Select the new Excel workbook as created in the previous step.
- A pop-up window will be presented showing the contents of the Excel workbook.
- In the “Column mapping” pane, select “Source code column” to be ‘Variable ID’.
- Select “Source name column” to be ‘ITEM’ to find concept descriptions in the CONCEPT table.
- Other settings may be necessary in some circumstances. Details here²³.
- Click “Import”. Using the data provided, USAGI searches the CONCEPT table for suitable matches to the data elements provided and returns the results to the main USAGI screen.

For the IASS the initial results are shown in Figure 11 below:

In the top pane is USAGI’s selection of the best match between the IASS data elements descriptions and the standard concepts in the CONCEPT table i.e. the standard vocabulary. USAGI also makes an assessment, between zero and one, of the quality of its own selection contained in the “Match score” column – 1 being an exact match.

²² Editing the existing downloaded ICHOM data dictionary itself to only contain these two columns was unsuccessful. USAGI raised errors on import.

²³ <https://www.ohdsi.org/web/wiki/doku.php?id=documentation:software:usagi>

The screenshot shows the USAGI main screen with the following sections:

- Source code table:**

Status	Source code	Source term	Frequency	Match score	Concept ID	Concept na...	Domain	Concept da...	Vocabulary	Concept code	Standard co...	Parents	Children	Comment
Unchecked	BASEOB	Obesity	1.00	45877450	Obesity	Meas Value	Answer	LOINC	LA6301-1	S	0	0		
Unchecked	HAQ2_Q07	HAQ-II Ques...	0.29	37111204	Penn Parkin...	Measurement Staging / Sc...	SNOMED	725843007	S	1	0	0		
Unchecked	SAE	Serious Adv...	0.76	45884383	Adverse event Meas Value	Answer	LOINC	LA7266-5	S	0	0	0		
Unchecked	BASEAMI	Myocardial I...	1.00	45881971	Myocardial I...	Meas Value	Answer	LOINC	LA14274-7	S	0	0	0	
Unchecked	HAQ2_Q08	HAQ-II Ques...	0.29	37111204	Penn Parkin...	Measurement Staging / Sc...	SNOMED	725843007	S	1	0	0		
Unchecked	IA_DIAG	Inflammator...	0.79	4291025	Arthritis	Condition	Clinical Find...	SNOMED	3723001	S	4	44		
Unchecked	HAQ2_Q09	HAQ-II Ques...	0.28	37111204	Penn Parkin...	Measurement Staging / Sc...	SNOMED	725843007	S	1	0	0		
Unchecked	DISDUR	Disease dur...	0.53	40758540	Exercise dur...	Observation	Clinical Obs...	LOINC	55411-3	S	5	0	0	
Unchecked	SAE_TYPE	Serious Adv...	0.60	45884383	Adverse event Meas Value	Answer	LOINC	LA7266-5	S	0	0	0		
Unchecked	HAQ2_Q10	HAQ-II Ques...	0.29	37111204	Penn Parkin...	Measurement Staging / Sc...	SNOMED	725843007	S	1	0	0		
Unchecked	BASEFRAC	Fracture	1.00	45876626	Fracture	Meas Value	Answer	LOINC	LA7437-2	S	0	0	0	
Unchecked	BASESTR	Stroke (excl...	0.59	373503	Transient ce...	Condition	Clinical Find...	SNOMED	266257000	S	2	8		
Unchecked	BASELUCED	Stroke (excl...	1.00	458550	Stroke (excl...	Condition	Clinical Find...	SNOMED	267855000	S	2	8		
- Target concepts table:**

Concept ID	Concept name	Domain	Concept class	Vocabulary	Concept code	Standard concept	Parents	Children
45877450	Obesity	Meas Value	Answer	LOINC	LA6301-1	S	0	0
- Search and Filters:**
 - Query:
 - Use source term as query:
 - Filters:
 - Filter by user selected concepts / ATC code
 - Filter by concept class:
 - Filter standard concepts
 - Filter by vocabulary:
 - Include source terms
 - Filter by domain:
- Results table:**

Score	Term	Concept ID	Concept name	Domain	Concept class	Vocabulary	Concept code	Standard concept	Parents	Children
1.00	Obesity	45877450	Obesity	Meas Value	Answer	LOINC	LA6301-1	S	0	0
1.00	Obesity	433736	Obesity	Condition	Clinical Finding	SNOMED	414916001	S	2	24
0.80	Obesity care	35622268	Obesity care	Observation	Procedure	SNOMED	763643007	S	1	0
0.79	Central obesity	4087487	Central obesity	Condition	Clinical Finding	SNOMED	248311001	S	1	5
0.72	Obesity medicine	1177393	Obesity medicine	Meas Value	Doc Subject Matter	LOINC	LP269243-4	S	0	0
0.70	Severe obesity	37018860	Severe obesity	Condition	Clinical Finding	SNOMED	83911000119104	S	1	4
- Comment:**
- Buttons:** , , ,
- Footer:** Approved / total: 0 / 52 0.0% of total frequency. Vocabulary version: v5.0 20-MAR-21

Figure 11: USAGI main screen

Each item in the top pane must be assessed in turn and marked ‘Approved’ if appropriate. When an item is highlighted in the top pane, alternatives to the mapped concept are available in the bottom (results) pane and these can replace the USAGI selection if required. Also, the selected concept can be removed resulting in the concept being ‘Unmapped’.²⁴

In this case, not all HAQ & HAQ II individual questions are in the vocabularies. However, an overall score for the HAQ II questionnaire is present and is mapped to HAQ II Question 1 for demonstration.

In a similar issue to the recording of multiple IA diagnoses, multiple serious adverse events (SAEs) should also be recordable. There is a limited number of FDA²⁵ defined SAEs: ‘Death’, ‘Life-threatening’, ‘Hospitalization’, ‘Disability or Permanent Damage’, ‘Congenital Anomaly/Birth Defect’, ‘Required intervention to Prevent Permanent Impairment or Damage (Devices)’, ‘Other Serious (Important Medical Events)’.

Ideally, each possible SAE would have its own Y/N field or column. This allows for efficient indexing and searching of the data. A bitmap or data munging approach is inefficient computationally and prone to programmatic errors. The final category, ‘Other Serious (Important Medical Events)’, requires a free-text field to record further details.

Each of the proposed mapping can be reviewed and when the user is satisfied with the mappings, they can be exported for inclusion in an OMOP-CDM instance using the following steps: Select menu item File/Export Source_to_Concept_Map. This creates a .csv file which can be appended to the OMOP-CDM and will be used to map the data that is subsequently presented for conversion. (See the draft

²⁴ Sometimes the row does not reflect the changes until you leave the row.

²⁵ Food & Drug Administration <https://www.fda.gov/safety/reporting-serious-problems-fda/what-serious-adverse-event>

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mappings in Appendices B & C). These mappings then need verification by ICHOM & the OHDSI vocabulary team.

Additional guidelines for this process include initially focussing on ‘Match Score’ to quickly deal with obviously correct mappings and focus on ‘Frequency’ to identify important codes worth expending effort on. For codes lacking a mapping or not worth significant effort, set CONCEPT_ID = 0.²⁶

The process for adding new standard concepts to the standard vocabularies is quite informal. The request can be discussed in the OHDSI forum and a use-case presented. If it is accepted by the vocabulary team, it will be included in a later version. In the interim, new concepts can be created locally.

What are the required entries in the standard vocabulary to accommodate the IASS?

- One entry in the CONCEPT table for the IASS. This will be used in the SURVEY_CONDUCT table in the SURVEY_CONCEPT_ID field to identify the survey instance as an IASS.
- Multiple entries in the CONCEPT table for the timing aspects of the IASS care pathway e.g. ‘Baseline’, ‘6 Month Review’, ‘Annual Review’, ‘18 Month Review’. These are to be created once and can be used for all standard sets. New standard sets may need additional timing concepts.
- One entry for each IASS data element not having a dedicated field i.e. all other than Type 0.
- One entry for each IASS answer type e.g. ‘Clinical Remission’. These are created once and can be used for all standard sets. New standard sets may need additional concepts.
- One entry for each Question/Answer combination e.g. comorbidities.

What are the required entries in the standard vocabulary to accommodate the IASS PROMS?

A number of PROMS are recommended in the IA reference guide. Their current representation in the standard vocabularies was assessed and is documented in Appendix E.

- One entry in the CONCEPT table for each recommended PROM. This will be used in the SURVEY_CONDUCT table in SURVEY_CONCEPT_ID to identify the survey instance as a PROM.
- One entry for each PROM answer type e.g. ‘Not at all’, ‘A little’, ‘A lot’. These will be created once and can then be used for all PROMS. New PROMS may need additional concepts.
- One entry for each Question/Answer combination e.g. comorbidities.

This concludes the analysis of the IASS for compatibility with the OMOP-CDM. The next section repeats much of this for the Localised Prostate Cancer Standard Set.

ETL of the Localised Prostate Cancer Standard Set (LPCSS)

Following the same procedure for the LPCSS and using the ‘Types’ discussed in the IASS above:

Objective 1: Identify gaps in the mapping of the LPCSS to the OMOP-CDM structures

What datatypes are in the LPCSS?

The datatypes found in the LPCSS matched those in the IASS.

Also similar to the IASS, some data elements (PRIMARYTX, SALVAGETX, COMPLRADDOMGRA, and COMORB) allow for multiple answers to a single question.

The PROMS questions in the LPCSS are fully enumerated in the data dictionary (LPCDD) and are typically as in the IASS.

From Figure 9

²⁶ <https://ohdsi.github.io/TheBookOfOhdsi/> (Chapter 6)

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The LPCDD elements are divided into groups: Patient factors, baseline tumour factors, pathological information, treatment variables, acute complications of treatment, patient-reported health status, and survival and disease control. These LPCSS elements are accommodated in the OMOP-CDM as follows:

Patient factors

Patient Factors	LPCSS Data Dictionary	Location in OMOP-CDM
Age	Date of Birth	TYPE 0: PERSON.YEAR_OF_BIRTH PERSON.MONTH_OF_BIRTH PERSON.DAY_OF_BIRTH
Comorbidities Physician-reported	- There are 12 Y/N questions recorded at baseline.	TYPE 1:

Baseline Tumor Factors

Baseline Tumor Factors	LPCSS Data Dictionary	OMOP-CDM
Date of histological diagnosis	DD/MM/YYYY	Type 2
Most recent PSA value before histological diagnosis	Numerical value of PSA level in ng/mL	Type 4
Clinical tumor stage	0 = cT0, 1 = cT1, 2 = cT1a, 3 = cT1b, 4 = cT1c, 5 = cT2, 6 = cT2a, 7 = cT2b, 8 = cT2c, 9 = cT3, 10 = cT3a, 11 = cT3b, 12 = cT4, 13 = cTX, 999 = Unknown	Type 6
Clinical nodal stage	0 = cN0, 1 = cN1, 2 = cNX, 999 = Unknown	Type 6
Number of biopsy cores taken	Numerical value of number of biopsy cores	Type 5
Number of biopsy cores positive	Numerical value of number of biopsy cores	Type 5
Greatest percentage involvement	Numerical value of greatest percentage involvement of any one biopsy core	Type 5
Gleason score: Primary	1-5	Type 7
Gleason score: Secondary	1-5	Type 7

Pathological Information

Pathological Information	LPCSS Data Dictionary	OMOP-CDM
Pathological tumor stage	1 = pT2, 2 = pT2a, 3 = pT2b, 4 = pT2c, 5 = pT3, 6 = pT3a, 7 = pT3b, 8 = pT4, 9 = pTX, 999 = Unkn.	Type 6
Pathological nodal stage	0 = pN0, 1 = pN1, 2 = pNX, 999 = Unknown	Type 6
Margin status	0 = Negative, 1 = Positive, 999 = Unknown	Type 6
Margin status focality	1 = Focal, 2 = Multi-focal, 999 = Unknown	Type 6
Pathological Gleason grade: Primary	1-5	Type 7
Pathological Gleason grade: Secondary	1-5	Type 7

Treatment Variables

Pathological Information	LPCSS Data Dictionary	OMOP-CDM
Treatment modalities used	1 = Watchful waiting, 2 = Active surveillance, 3 = Radical prostatectomy, 4 = External beam radiation therapy (primary treatment or adjuvant following surgery), 5 = Brachytherapy, 6 = Androgen deprivation therapy, 7 = Focal therapy (free text), 888 = Other (free text)	Type 1
Type of focal therapy	Primary treatment modality	Type 3
Date watchful waiting initiated	DD/MM/YYYY	Type 2
Date active surveillance initiated	DD/MM/YYYY	Type 2
Date of primary radical prostatectomy	DD/MM/YYYY	Type 2
Primary nerve sparing status	1 = Non-nerve-sparing, 2 = Nerve-sparing	Type 6

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Primary external Beam Radiation Therapy: Dose (Gray)	Numerical value of dose in Gray (###)	Type 4
Primary external Beam Radiation Therapy: Average dose per fraction (Gray)	Numerical value of average dose per fraction in Gray (##.#)	Type 4
Start date of primary external beam radiation therapy	DD/MM/YYYY	Type 2
Stop date of primary external beam radiation therapy	DD/MM/YYYY	Type 2
Ongoing primary external beam radiation therapy	1 = Treatment ongoing	Type 6
Start date of primary brachytherapy	DD/MM/YYYY	Type 2
Stop date of primary brachytherapy	DD/MM/YYYY	Type 2
Ongoing primary brachytherapy	1 = Treatment ongoing	Type 6
Primary brachytherapy dose	1 = Low dose, 2 = High dose, 999 = Unknown	Type 6
Start date of primary androgen deprivation therapy	DD/MM/YYYY	Type 2
Stop date of primary androgen deprivation therapy	DD/MM/YYYY	Type 2
Ongoing primary androgen deprivation therapy	1 = Treatment ongoing	Type 6
Start date of primary focal therapy	DD/MM/YYYY	Type 2
Stop date of primary focal therapy	DD/MM/YYYY	Type 2
Ongoing primary focal therapy	1 = Treatment ongoing	Type 6
Primary treatment modality other than those explicitly listed	Primary treatment modality	Type 3
Start date of other primary therapy	DD/MM/YYYY	Type 2
Stop date of other primary therapy	DD/MM/YYYY	Type 2
Ongoing other therapy	1 = Treatment ongoing	Type 6
Salvage treatment initiated (within last year?)	0 = No, 1 = Yes	Type 6
Salvage treatment modalities used	1 = Radical prostatectomy, 2 = External beam radiation therapy, 3 = Brachytherapy, 4 = Androgen deprivation therapy, 5 = Focal therapy, 888 = Other	Type 1
Salvage treatment modality other than those explicitly listed	Salvage treatment modality	Type 3
Date of radical prostatectomy	DD/MM/YYYY	Type 2
Nerve sparing status	1 = Non-nerve-sparing, 2 = Nerve-sparing	Type 6
External Beam Radiation Therapy: Dose (Gray)	Numerical value of dose in Gray (###)	Type 4
External Beam Radiation Therapy: Average dose per fraction (Gray)	Numerical value of average dose per fraction in Gray (##.#)	Type 4
Start date of external beam radiation therapy	DD/MM/YYYY	Type 2
Stop date of external beam radiation therapy	DD/MM/YYYY	Type 2
Ongoing external beam radiation therapy	1 = Treatment ongoing	Type 6
Start date of brachytherapy	DD/MM/YYYY	Type 2
Stop date of brachytherapy	DD/MM/YYYY	Type 2
Ongoing brachytherapy	1 = Treatment ongoing	Type 6
Brachytherapy dose	1 = Low dose, 2 = High dose, 999 = Unknown	Type 6
Start date of androgen deprivation therapy	DD/MM/YYYY	Type 2
Stop date of androgen deprivation therapy	DD/MM/YYYY	Type 2
Ongoing androgen deprivation therapy	1 = Treatment ongoing	Type 6
Start date of focal therapy	DD/MM/YYYY	Type 2

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Stop date of focal therapy	DD/MM/YYYY	Type 2
Ongoing focal therapy	1 = Treatment ongoing	Type 6
Start date of other therapy	DD/MM/YYYY	Type 2
Stop date of other therapy	DD/MM/YYYY	Type 2
Ongoing other therapy	1 = Treatment ongoing	Type 6

Acute Complications of Treatment

Acute Complications of Treatment	LPCSS Data Dictionary	OMOP-CDM
Clavien complication (maximum grade)	0 = No, 1 = Yes, grade 3, 2 = Yes, grade 4	Type 6
CTCAE grade 3 or 4 complication during treatment or within 6 months after completing treatment	0 = No, 1 = Yes	Type 6
CTCAE domain and grade	0 = No grade 3 or 4 toxicity, 1 = Fatigue grade 3 2 = Fatigue grade 4, 3 = Dermatitis grade 3, 4 = Dermatitis grade 4, 5 = Diarrhea grade 3, 6 = Diarrhea grade 4, 7 = Abdominal pain grade 3 8 = Abdominal pain grade 4, 9 = Rectal mucositis grade 3, 10 = Rectal mucositis grade 4 11 = Proctitis grade 3, 12 = Proctitis grade 4 13 = Hot flashes grade 3, 14 = Hot flashes grade 4, 15 = Cystitis non-infective grade 3, 16 = Cystitis non-infective grade 4, 17 = Urinary retention grade 3, 18 = Urinary retention grade 4, 19 = Other grade 3 (free text), 20 = Other grade 4 (free text)	Type 6
CTCAE domain other than those explicitly listed	CTCAE domain	Type 3

Neither of the recommended PROMs, EPIC-26 nor LIBID, are currently present in the standard vocabularies. Both consist exclusively of **Type 6** questions.

Disease Control

Disease Control	LPCSS Data Dictionary	OMOP-CDM
Death: Patient died	0 = No, 1 = Yes	Type 6
Death: Date of death	DD/MM/YYYY	Type 2
Cause of death: Death attributable to localized prostate cancer	0 = No, 1 = Yes, 999 = Unknown	Type 6
Disease control: Metastasis	0 = No, 1 = Yes	Type 6
Disease control: Date metastasis identified	DD/MM/YYYY	Type 2
Disease control: Biochemical recurrence	0 = No, 1 = Yes	Type 6
Disease control: Date biochemical recurrence identified	DD/MM/YYYY	Type 2
Disease control: Biochemical recurrence PSA value	Numerical value of PSA level in ng/mL	Type 4

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Objective 2: Identify gaps in the mapping of the LPCSS to the OMOP-CDM vocabulary.

Following the same steps as for the Inflammatory Arthritis standard set above yielded the mapping in Appendix C.

This concludes the assessment of the IASS and LPCSS data dictionaries to identify gaps in mapping the structure and their metadata to the OMOP-CDM.

A practical exercise to map simulated IASS data to the OMOP follows.

From Figure 9

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5.2.3 Mapping simulated IASS survey data to the OMOP-CDM:

If an ICHOM committed institution presents a dataset - reflecting verbatim the inflammatory arthritis data dictionary format - for conversion to the OMOP-CDM format, a single record in the data set might look like Figure 12.

N/A	AGE	SEX	SOCIO	SMOKIN	BASEHBP	BASEAM	BASESTR	...	REM_LD	REM_LDA_R	IDA	IDA_RES
Patient ID	Age	Sex at birt	Education	Smoking s	High blood	Myocardia	Stroke	...	Disease at	Disease activi	Inflamma	Inflammatory disease activity result
5001	49	1	3	0	0	0	0	...	3		1	Sample M Sample Measure answer

Figure 12: Single record representing a patient’s ICHOM standard set (one survey instance)

If the OMOP-CDM is to accommodate management of ICHOM standard sets, some additional metadata fields are necessary:

- Date of administration: What date was the PROM administered?
- Where, in the care plan timing logic, was the PROM administered?

The presented dataset might now look like Figure 13. Additional repeating annual and 6-monthly records may also be present.

N/A	Date of PROM	TimingConceptID	AGE	SEX	SOCIO	SMOKIN	BASEHBP	BASEAM	BASESTR	...	REM_LD	REM_LDA	IDA	IDA_RES
Patient ID	Date of Administration of PROM	Timing Concept	Age	Sex at birt	Education	Smoking s	High blood	Myocardia	Stroke	...	Disease at	Disease ac	Inflamma	Inflammatory disease activity result
5001	10th June 2018	Baseline & PROM	49	1	3	0	0	0	0	...	3		1	Sample Me; Sample Measure answer
5001	10th Dec 2018	6-Monthly Clinical Form	Blank	Blank	Blank	Blank	Blank	Blank	Blank	...	3		1	Sample Me; Sample Measure answer
5001	12th June 2019	Annual Clinical & PROM	Blank	Blank	Blank	Blank	0	0	0	...	3		1	Sample Me; Sample Measure answer
5001	10th Dec 2018	6-Monthly Clinical Form	Blank	Blank	Blank	Blank	Blank	Blank	Blank	...	3		1	Sample Me; Sample Measure answer

Figure 13: Enhanced records, each one representing a patient’s ICHOM standard set (one line per survey instance)

Additional data about the survey instance may also be present e.g. Survey_Start_Date, Survey_End_Date, Provide_ID and details about the collection methods. Full details of the SURVEY_CONDUCT fields are to be found here https://github.com/OHDSI/CommonDataModel/wiki/SURVEY_CONDUCT

STEP: Copying the .csv/excel file into a database for further processing (SQL Server) yields the following:

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Results		Messages													
	PatientID	DateOfProm	Timing	AGE	SEX	SOCIO	SMOKING	BASEHBP	BASEAMI	BASESTR	REM_LDA_TARG	REM_LDA_REAC	IDA	IDA_RES	
1	5001	01/02/2017	Baseline & PROM	49	1	3	0	0	0	0	3	1	Sample Measure Name	Sample Measure answer	
2	5001	01/07/2017	6-monthly Clinical Review	49	1	3	0	0	0	0	3	1	Sample Measure Name	Sample Measure answer	
3	5001	01/02/2018	Annual & PROM	49	1	3	0	0	0	0	3	1	Sample Measure Name	Sample Measure answer	
4	5001	01/07/2018	6-monthly Clinical Review	49	1	3	0	0	0	0	3	1	Sample Measure Name	Sample Measure answer	
5	5001	01/02/2019	Annual & PROM	49	1	3	0	0	0	0	3	1	Sample Measure Name	Sample Measure answer	

STEP: In order to have each question/response combination as a separate entry in the OBSERVATION table, the data above must be unpivoted²⁷. This reflects the format proposed in earlier work (See Appendix A) and yields the following.

	PatientID	DateOfProm	Timing	Questions	Answers
23	5001	01/02/2018	Annual & PROM	AGE	49
24	5001	01/02/2018	Annual & PROM	SEX	1
25	5001	01/02/2018	Annual & PROM	SOCIO	3
26	5001	01/02/2018	Annual & PROM	SMOKING	0
27	5001	01/02/2018	Annual & PROM	BASEHBP	0
28	5001	01/02/2018	Annual & PROM	BASEAMI	0
29	5001	01/02/2018	Annual & PROM	BASESTR	0
30	5001	01/02/2018	Annual & PROM	REM_LDA_TARG	3
31	5001	01/02/2018	Annual & PROM	REM_LDA_REAC	1
32	5001	01/02/2018	Annual & PROM	IDA	Sample Measure Name
33	5001	01/02/2018	Annual & PROM	IDA_RES	Sample Measure answer
34	5001	01/07/2018	6-monthly Clinical Rev...	AGE	49
...

²⁷ <https://docs.microsoft.com/en-us/sql/t-sql/queries/from-using-pivot-and-unpivot?view=sql-server-ver15>

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Step: Alter this table to add the additional columns in preparation for insertion into the OBSERVATION table²⁸. See Appendix C for an explanation of the relevant OBSERVATION fields.

The following steps are then taken to import the data into the OMOP-CDM instance.

- Insert new concepts into CONCEPT
- Insert new ancestors into CONCEPT_ANCESTOR
- Insert new relationships into CONCEPT_RELATIONSHIP
- Insert survey instances into SURVEY_CONDUCT
- Append from test-table to OBSERVATION
- Insert new vocabulary entry into VOCABULARY

5.2.4 Generalising this approach for other standard sets

The ICHOM specific ETL has two cycles: First, the data dictionary is processed and second, the data itself is processed. Both are subject to similar analysis steps represented in Figure 14 below, the data dictionary analysis following the **red** path and the data itself following the **green** path. Institutions can choose from a variety of PROMs and therefore, while it might initially appear that Cycle 1 need only be executed the first time a specific standard set is processed, it is advisable to execute both cycles for each ETL to allow for variations in the PROMs selected.

Figure 14: ICHOM specific ETL cycles

Cycle 1 – The Standard Set Data Dictionary (Red path)

Establish if the Standard Set contains adequate metadata.

- What is the date of creation of the data row? This might be the date the PROM was completed.

²⁸ <https://github.com/OHDSI/CommonDataModel/wiki/OBSERVATION>

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- Where in the ICHOM care-pathway does it belong? Baseline, annual review etc. If this is missing, then it will be difficult to execute accurate comparisons.

Scan the data dictionary (DD) for exceptions to the following answer types: Numeric, date, text, categorical (enumerated). If the data elements fall within these types, they can all be accommodated in the OMOP-CDM.

Scan the DD for data elements designed to accommodate multiple answers e.g. IA_DIAG in the IASS. If any exist, consider splitting these into separate data elements. Also, consider whether each of these separate elements requires an additional qualifying field such as date_of_diagnosis. If there are too many possible answers for this approach, consider alternatives e.g. using free text followed by a concept search in Cycle 2.

Alternatively, these multiple answers can be represented by question-answer pairs being created as standard concepts e.g. ‘Which IA variation do you suffer from – Rheumatoid Arthritis’, mapped to the standard concept Rheumatoid Arthritis with domain = condition. Similarly, a standard concept would be created for psoriatic arthritis, juvenile idiopathic arthritis, and ankylosing spondylitis.

Only one PROM is included in the data dictionary. Accordingly, scan the data elements in the other PROMS recommended in the standard set reference guide for compatibility with the OMOP-CDM as in the previous two steps above. If the required PROM is not in the vocabulary, then consider applying to have it included through the EHDEN forums. Add as new concepts (>2B) in the interim.

Map the obvious data dictionary fields to their equivalents in the OMOP-CDM e.g. patient date-of-birth, sex-at-birth etc.

Process the standard set data dictionary through USAGI to identify data dictionary elements having no matching standard concept in the standard vocabularies.

Create new standard concepts in the standard vocabularies for these missing concepts.

Reprocess the standard set data dictionary through USAGI to confirm that all necessary data dictionary elements have a mapped standard concept in the standard vocabularies.

Use USAGI to create the Source_to_Concept_Map file which defines these mappings.

Append these to the standard vocabularies.

Create ancillary relationships in the OMOP-CDM.

- Add new CONCEPT_ID to the CONCEPT table. The convention is that it be >2Billion, the new concept is considered ‘STANDARD’, valid from 1970-01-01 00:00:00 to 2099-12-31 00:00:00 with INVALID_REASON = NULL.
- Add new VOCABULARY_ID to the VOCABULARY table. The convention is that it not clash with any OMOP standard vocabularies.
- Add “Maps to” and “Mapped from” records to the CONCEPT_RELATIONSHIP table indicating both relationships to itself i.e. where CONCEPT_ID_1 and CONCEPT_ID_2 are the new CONCEPT_ID.
- Add a new record to the CONCEPT_ANCESTOR table, with ANCESTOR_CONCEPT_ID and DESCENDANT_CONCEPT_ID both equal to the new CONCEPT_ID.
- Add entries to the SOURCE TO CONCEPT MAP table mapping the source codes to the new concepts.

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Cycle 2 – The Data (Green path)

Review the data. Does the data correspond with the data dictionary? If not, can the differing data elements be accommodated in the OMOP-CDM?

Is the selected PROM the same as in that the data dictionary? Is the PROM title, its questions and responses in the standard vocabularies? If not, these should be created as standard concepts.²⁹

Process the data through USAGI to identify data contents having no matching standard concept in the standard vocabularies.

Create new standard concepts in the standard vocabularies for these missing concepts.

Reprocess the standard set data dictionary through USAGI to confirm that all necessary data contents have a mapped standard concept in the standard vocabularies.

Use USAGI to create the Source_to_Concept_Map file which defines these mappings.

Append these to the standard vocabularies.

Create ancillary relationships in the OMOP-CDM.

5.2.5 Apply the method to the Advanced Prostate Cancer standard set

Again, as we are using synthetic data, only the red path was executed. There were no exceptions to the expected data types. Several of the questions were presented as Type 1 and can be dealt with as in the previous standard sets. The recommended PROMS³⁰ contained primarily Type 6 questions, however, minor variation was introduced as several were presented as matrix questions. These can be dealt with as Type 6. An additional question-type was introduced with semantic differential scales. This answer requires the patient to respond on a non-slider rating scale from 1 (very poor) to 7 (excellent) regarding their overall health and quality of life. Creating new standard concepts for ‘very poor’ and ‘excellent’ are possible but there is no definition of the increments 2 through 6. Without these, it appears that analysis would have to be on the basis of the numerical value.

Using the automated USAGI concept matching function yielded a patchy mapping as in the previous standard sets. As before, significant input from clinicians and vocabulary experts will be needed to complete this mapping.

The main conclusion from using the generalised approach above is that the creation of this initial mapping is a quick exercise, needing no more than a few hours.

5.3 Data analytics design

5.3.1 Introduction

A key purpose of converting data sources to the OMOP-CDM is to facilitate networked research through the execution of standardised analytics against the standardised data. Concept sets and cohort definitions are building blocks for these analytics. Creation of these concept sets and cohort

²⁹ This describes the situation where the names of the data elements as well as the contents of the data elements are both to be assessed in USAGI for appropriate mappings. An example in the IASS is inflammatory disease activity (IDA). The value that is stored in this field could exist as a standard concept in the standard vocabularies and if so, this mapping should be made in this phase.

³⁰ EPIC 26 Short form https://medicine.umich.edu/sites/default/files/content/downloads/EPIC-SF-6.2002_0.pdf and <https://www.eortc.org/app/uploads/sites/2/2018/08/Specimen-PR25-English-1.1.pdf> and <https://www.eortc.org/app/uploads/sites/2/2018/08/Specimen-QLQ-C30-English.pdf>

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definitions in the Atlas environment provided some additional feedback on the quality and completeness of the mapping process. It also showed how key elements of the ICHOM standard sets are incorporated in the formulation of a research question:

- How a PROM can be the measured outcome of interest.
- How baseline characteristics can be incorporated as case-mix variables and risk-adjustment.
- How varying treatment regimens’ effect of outcomes is studied.

This phase took an exploratory approach with the primary objective of adding to the knowledge gained from the prior ETL process. It looked to the existing work on benchmarking, network research and the rheumatoid arthritis study-a-thon in the EHDEN environment for guidance.

5.3.2 Preliminary decisions

Three preliminary decisions are required in advance of addressing a research question (RQ):

- What analysis strategy will be deployed?
- What analysis implementation will be used?
- What deployment method and architecture will be implemented?

Analysis strategy

The analysis strategy chosen should depend on the type of research carried out. Some of these are represented in Figure 15. The ‘Single study’ works for typical RQs e.g. comparing drug effects. ‘Real-time queries’ may be more suitable for monitoring and control and ‘Large-scale analytics’ for exhaustive analysis of large and complex datasets.

Figure 15: Analysis strategy (from Book of OHDSI)

In this work, ‘Single Study’ is the appropriate analysis strategy for our population level estimation question as the path from patient-level data in the CDM to reliable evidence.

Analysis implementation

The analysis implementation defines how the code for the execution of the analysis will be developed. OHDSI-Atlas provides a ready-to-go environment for the creation of concept-sets, cohorts and the generation of a study package using R code. If that is not flexible or comprehensive enough to address the RQs, addition code can be written calling the OHDSI Methods Library or writing custom code. In the context of a ‘Single study’ analysis strategy, the implementation would address the ‘Develop code’ step.

Figure 16: Analysis implementation (from Book of OHDSI)

Referring to Figure 16 above: In this work, a hybrid of ‘Custom’ and ‘Standard’, using the Atlas environment, was the appropriate initial analysis implementation strategy for our population level estimation question as the path from patient-level data in the CDM to reliable evidence. It is likely that the OHDSI Methods Library also could have been usefully employed however this was not needed here.

Architecture and deployment

The next decision is the deployment method and architecture for the research environment. The main decision here is whether to execute the research in ‘public’ environment, bring it in-house into a local environment, or run a hybrid of the two. It is hoped to have an integrated Arachne/Atlas/EHDEN environment in the future with data storage facilities. Currently there is no facility to store a user’s data in this ‘public’ environment.

Figure 17: ‘public’ and ‘local’ deployment architectures

In this work, the ‘public’ ATLAS environment was used in the first phase for defining concept sets and cohorts and generation of the study package. The process then crossed over to a locally installed OMOP-CDM on the researcher’s local PC. This crossover was a pragmatic solution, necessary due to technical limitations in both paths.

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5.3.3 Defining the research questions (RQs)

There are three primary types of RQs which can be addressed using the OHDSI toolset: Characterisation, population level estimate (PLE), and patient level prediction (PLP). Further classes of questions can be explored writing custom code (see Figure 16) against the OMOP-CDM.

Characterisation questions

Characterisation answers question about a dataset, the persons in the dataset, the persons in a cohort. In IA, example characterisation questions are:

- For patients newly diagnosed with IA, what proportion were prescribed NSAIDS in 2019?
- For patients newly diagnosed with IA, what proportion were prescribed DMARDS in 2019?
- Are these NSAID/DMARDS proportions different from 2018?
- What is the average age of patients newly diagnosed with IA?

The outputs to this type of question are typically counts, percentages etc. and may be presented as numbers, bar-charts, distributions or more complex visualisations. Other typical question formulations and outputs are to be found in the Book of OHDSI³¹.

Population-level Estimation (PLE) questions

PLE can support causal inferences about the effects of healthcare interventions and provide answers to questions like: What are the causal effects of a medication? Which treatment works better? What is the risk of an adverse event as a result of an intervention? In IA, example pharmacological, patient reported PLE questions are:

- For patients newly diagnosed with IA, does treatment with NSAIDS compared to treatment with DMARDS result in better outcomes based on ‘Pain’?
- For patients newly diagnosed with IA, does treatment with NSAIDS compared to treatment with DMARDS result in better outcomes based on ‘Activity Limitation’?

Similarly, example pharmacological, clinician reported PLE questions are:

- For patients newly diagnosed with IA, does treatment with NSAIDS compared to treatment with DMARDS result in better outcomes based on ‘Inflammatory Disease Activity’?
- For patients newly diagnosed with IA, does treatment with NSAIDS compared to treatment with DMARDS result in better outcomes based on ‘Response/Remission’?

Continuing, example **non-pharmacological**, patient reported PLE questions are:

- For patients newly diagnosed with IA, does therapy ‘Exercise’ compared to therapy ‘Rest’ result in better outcomes based on ‘Pain’?
- For patients newly diagnosed with IA, does therapy ‘Exercise’ compared to therapy ‘Rest’ result in better outcomes based on ‘Activity Limitation’?

Similarly, example **non-pharmacological**, clinician reported PLE questions are:

- For patients newly diagnosed with IA, does therapy ‘Exercise’ compared to therapy ‘Rest’ result in better outcomes based on ‘Inflammatory Disease Activity’?
- For patients newly diagnosed with IA, does therapy ‘Exercise’ compared to therapy ‘Rest’ result in better outcomes based on ‘Response/Remission’?

The outputs to this type of question are typically relative risk, average treatment effect, correlation, association etc. These types of questions are commonly known as comparative cohort questions or comparative effect estimation questions and are subject to advanced design principles to ensure

³¹ <https://ohdsi.github.io/TheBookOfOhdsi/> P.102-104

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internal and external validity of the results. Direct effect estimation questions estimate the effect of an exposure on an outcome, as compared to no exposure e.g.

- For patients newly diagnosed with IA, does therapy ‘Exercise’ compared to ‘No Exercise’ result in better outcomes based on ‘Pain’?

Patient-level Prediction (PLP) questions

Patient level prediction tries to answer the question: What will happen to a specific patient? In IA, an example clinician reported PLP question is:

- For patients newly diagnosed with IA subsequently undergoing surgery, what is the probability that the patient will suffer a severe adverse consequence within 12 months of surgery?

Ideally, characterisation questions would be initially addressed allowing us to gain familiarity with our dataset, develop intuitive knowledge of the data set, potentially identify data quality issues and other insights. Initially, features available in the atlas environment such as Charlson Index, Age, Observation times, drug exposures etc will be used.

However, in this case, PLE questions are more useful in achieving our objectives and will be addressed following the examples above and PLP questions will not be addressed in this work.

The inputs/governing documents are outlined Figure 18 below.

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Figure 18: Inputs/Outputs to generate ICHOM IASS study package

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RQ in this research

Deliverable 3.2 details how PLE research attempts to emulate a randomised clinical trial. Patients observed to receive one intervention are compared to patients observed to receive another intervention. The main design choices in such a comparative cohort design are the definitions of the target, comparator and outcome cohorts, the time-at-risk and the model used to estimate the effect. It is key to ensure that patients in the target and comparator cohorts do not systematically differ from each other.

Problem definition

DMARDS are a long-term disease altering medications sometimes needing months to take effect with NSAIDS often prescribed for pain-relief in the interim. Therefore, the choice between NSAIDS and DMARDS as a treatment for inflammatory arthritis pain may not be a valid therapeutic decision. Nonetheless, this was used as an example domain question. As this exercise did not intend reaching conclusive findings from the simulated data, addressing this question was adequate. The concept set and cohort creation phases for following comparative estimation question were addressed here:

- For patients newly diagnosed with IA, does treatment with NSAIDS compared to treatment with DMARDS result in better outcomes based on ‘Pain’?

Target and comparator cohorts

Patients were considered ‘newly diagnosed’ if they received a first diagnosis of any of Rheumatoid Arthritis, Psoriatic Arthritis, Ankylosing Spondylitis, or Juvenile Idiopathic Arthritis. Patients must have had at least one year of prior continuous observation in the database before first diagnosis and have had a recorded prescription of NSAIDS or DMARDS following the first diagnosis to enter the cohorts.

Outcome cohort

In the IASS, pain is a patient reported outcome. Implementations of the standard set may use any of six IA pain surveys: Numerical rating scale, visual analogue scale, SF-36 bodily pain, RAND bodily pain, PROMIS pain interference, or PedsQL3.0 Arthritis module pain and hurt. Pain scores should be recorded after the prescription date. The outcome cohort consists of those patients from the target and comparator cohorts who have a recorded pain outcome. All of these instruments have been linked to a standardised reporting metric so that outcomes can be compared between users of the standard set irrespective of their choice of instrument. Linked scores are available here³². The visual analogue scale exists in the standard vocabularies and was selected as the outcome of interest.

Time-at-risk

Any time in the dataset

Model, feasibility/diagnostics, propensity scoring, formal protocol, data quality analysis.

Other steps recommended in The Book of OHDSI were not executed in this study.

5.4 Data analytics execution in Atlas

To implement this study, several phases were executed in the public Atlas³³ environment. Within EHDEN, the intention is to export the executable R package to the Arachne environment or similar environment where it will be linked to a data node containing real-world data in OMOP-CDM format. This package can include concept set definitions, cohort definitions, characterisations, and the population level estimation study package any other underlying logic necessary to analyse or implement the ICHOM IASS. Additional code may be necessary in the Arachne environment to execute

³² <http://tihealthcare.nl/en/expertise/common-metrics>

³³ <https://test-atlas.ehden.eu/>

analyses specific to the ICHOM use-case. Due to limitations in the EHDEN/Arachne environment, particularly the lack of facility to store and make available datasets, the study package was transferred in modules to the researcher’s PC.

5.4.1 Create concept sets for the IASS

First, the concept sets were created defining the conditions the diagnoses required in order to be included in the cohort. The IASS identified the relevant conditions as Rheumatoid Arthritis, Psoriatic Arthritis, Ankylosing Spondylitis and Juvenile Idiopathic Arthritis. A new concept set was created for each of these four conditions. The concept set for Rheumatoid Arthritis was created with all descendants. This is how the Rheumatoid Arthritis concept set now looked.

Figure 19: Rheumatoid arthritis concept set

Using the same steps, new concept sets for Psoriatic Arthritis, Ankylosing Spondylitis, and Juvenile Idiopathic Arthritis were created. Further concept sets for the interventions DMARDs and NSAIDs were also created: DMARDs created from the outputs of the RA study-a-thon and NSAIDs from a basic query to Athena³⁴.

An additional concept set intended to identify patients with pain scores was also created but this is a somewhat contrived approach. Comparison of pain scores could be included as a characterisation question or even ignored until the final analytics phase.

These concept sets are the building blocks for creating the cohorts. The process of creating concept sets from the standard vocabularies is a key step in defining the phenotypes for the research question. In this exploratory work, practical choices were made by the author. For decision systems, choice of what vocabulary to include in the concept sets requires both domain expertise i.e. inflammatory arthritis and vocabulary expertise.

5.4.2 Create cohorts of interest for the IASS

In this study, the cohort definitions identify patients who have the conditions defined in the IASS i.e. the patients of interest have one of the IA conditions and received either DMARDs or NSAIDs.

There are three main ways to populate a cohort: Cohort entry events (initial conditions), Inclusion Criteria, and Cohort Exit. Cohort entry events can belong to any of the OMOP-CDM domains e.g. Conditions, Drugs, Procedure etc. Each of these criteria can be modified using the ‘Add Criteria’ function. The criteria offered in the dropdown list are specific to the domain of the initial condition. All previously defined concept sets are valid cohort entry events and the only additional criteria added was that the condition occurrence was the first time in the person’s history. Entry to the cohort can

³⁴ <https://athena.ohdsi.org/search-terms/terms>

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be restricted by a similar mechanism where any domain can be used to exclude entry e.g. patients receiving a particular drug in a timeframe can be excluded. Existence of a pain score could also be used at this point though this is too specific to the current question and would probably invalidate the cohort as a phenotype definition for subsequent use. None were used in this cohort definition.

Inclusion criteria is the second mechanism for populating the cohort.

The comparator cohort followed similar development steps. No Cohort Exit was defined in this case. The Cohort Definition now looks like this.

The screenshot shows the ATLAS Cohort Definition interface for Cohort #45, titled "ICHOM SS Inflammatory Arthritis". The interface is divided into several sections:

- Cohort Entry Events:** This section lists four criteria for cohort entry, each based on a condition occurrence of a specific ICHOM SS IA (Juvenile Idiopath..., Ankylosing Spond..., Psoriatic Arthritis, and Rheumatoid Arthr...). Each criterion is set to occur "for the first time in the person's history". There are buttons to "Add attribute...", "Delete Criteria", and "Restrict initial events".
- Inclusion Criteria:** A section for defining inclusion criteria, currently showing "New inclusion criteria" and a limit of "earliest event" per person.
- Cohort Exit:** A section for defining cohort exit criteria, currently showing "Event Persistence" set to "end of continuous observation" and "Censoring Events" with "No censoring events selected".
- Cohort Eras:** A section for defining cohort eras, currently showing "Specify era collapse gap size" set to "0" days and a link to "add trimming options...".

The interface also includes a sidebar with navigation options like Home, Data Sources, Search, Concept Sets, Cohort Definitions, Characterizations, Cohort Pathways, Incidence Rates, Profiles, Estimation, Prediction, Jobs, Configuration, and Feedback. The bottom of the screen shows a Windows taskbar with various application icons.

Figure 20: Cohort definition screenshot

5.4.3 Create & Execute study package

As this work progressed and the objectives became more clearly defined, the value of investing in the creation and execution of a study package, without real-world benchmarking data and questions diminished. It did not appear that these steps would add value at this point. However, a brief outline of the planned steps is included here for future work with RWD.

When the concept sets and cohorts have been defined, cohort characterization can be executed. This step generates cohort level descriptive summary statistics such as count, mean, min, max, standard

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deviation, median and ranges from person level covariate data. At this point it would also be possible to characterise the cohorts by pain scores. Following this, the PLE questions are then defined to answer the specific research questions. When these have been defined the code can be downloaded in the form of an R-package and ‘brought’ to the data.

The R-package can now be executed against the data in OMOP-CDM format from the previous phase and the results analysed. The study package can be run against multiple datasets and the results compared or benchmarked if appropriate. At this time, the sole source of benchmarking information available is ICHOM’s GLOBE benchmarking report. It offers some guidance on metrics that may be appropriate for benchmarking in this context. However, it is not designed for a retrospective observational data scenario. There are obvious parallels between benchmarking exercises and OHDSI’s network studies where multiple data owners provide aggregated data for analysis. GLOBE’s key characteristics are compared to the current analysis below and may provide some useful guidance for future benchmarking exercises. However, this is beyond the scope of this report.

5.5 Main findings

The main findings from the preceding mapping and analytics phases are summarised below

5.5.1 Objective 1 findings:

Finding 1: The data types in the IASS and in the LPCSS can all be accommodated in the OMOP-CDM i.e. all the data types are numeric, date, text/string, categorical/numerical.

Finding 2: Some data elements in the IASS and the LPCSS can be directly accommodated i.e. matched in specific tables/fields in the OMOP-CDM e.g. ‘Age’ can be directly stored in PERSON.YEAR_OF_BIRTH. There is no requirement for mapping these fields to a standard concept.

Finding 3: Other data elements in the IASS and the LPCSS can be directly accommodated in a specific field as in Finding 2. However, the source data must be mapped to a standard concept from the standardised vocabulary. For example, ‘Sex’ in the IASS is represented as 1,2, or 999 meaning M, F, or unknown respectively. This is mapped to a standard concept e.g. 45880669, 45878463, or 45877986 before storage in a specific field, PERSON.GENDER_CONCEPT_ID.

Finding 4: Other standard set data elements do not have a table/field dedicated or clearly identified for their storage in the OMOP-CDM. The general approach to representing these data elements is:

- 1) Identify a standard concept to which they can be mapped and
- 2) Find the appropriate table/field in which they should be stored.

An example of such a data element in the IASS is ‘Education’ which uses the International Standard Classification of Education³⁵, a scale (0-6) representing pre-primary through tertiary education. This element can be mapped through use of the OBSERVATION table in the field, VALUE_AS_NUMBER and, if available in the standard vocabulary, in field VALUE_AS_CONCEPT_ID where the CONCEPT_ID would be one of the classifications (‘Pre-Primary’...‘Tertiary’).

³⁵ <http://uis.unesco.org/en/topic/international-standard-classification-education-isced>

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Finding 5: Each standard concept belongs to a single domain and this domain dictates which event table the information must be stored in i.e. if the standard concept belongs to the ‘observation’ domain, then the data mapped to this standard concept will be stored in the OBSERVATION table. In other cases, the domain may be ‘procedure’, ‘measurement’, ‘condition’, or ‘drug’ and the data element is stored in the PROCEDURE_OCCURRENCE, MEASUREMENT, CONDITION_OCCURRENCE, OR DRUG_EXPOSURE tables respectively.

Following from this, the simplest version of ETL is if all data elements in an ICHOM standard set are deemed to be ‘observations’. Then, most standard set data will be stored in the OBSERVATION table, except demographics which are stored in the PERSON table.

Finding 6: The data types in the PROMs recommended in the IASS and the LPCSS can all be accommodated in the OMOP-CDM. i.e. all the data types are numeric, date, text/string, categorical/numerical. Many are Likert scales with numerical equivalents which can be dealt with as ‘Education’ in Finding 4 above. One question in the APCSS introduced an additional question/answer type, non-slider rating scale from 1 (very poor) to 7 (excellent). There is no obvious method to map the answers at this time.

Finding 7: OMOP-CDM V6 includes a table named SURVEY_CONDUCT dedicated to administration of surveys/PROMs. This, in conjunction with standard concepts, provides the structure to implement ICHOM’s timing logic or care-pathways. Earlier versions of the CDM have no such table and the management of surveys is much more cumbersome but may still be feasible with custom ETL coding.

Finding 8: The use of answers allowing multiple responses in ICHOM’s standard sets are structurally problematic. However, this can be resolved by replacing these questions/answers with a series of questions/answers, each one dedicated to one of the possible answer options.

Finding 9: The method applied to the IA and LPCSS was generalised and subsequently applied successfully to this phase of analysing the APCSS.

5.5.2 Objective 2 findings:

Finding 1: There are three levels at which the representation of the standard sets in the standard vocabularies need consideration: First, the data elements in the data dictionary, second, the contents of some of these data elements, and third, the PROMs recommended in the standard sets and their question/answers.

Finding 2: It is inconclusive from the published conventions (both ICHOM and OHDSI) how to classify survey question/answers into domains i.e. observations, measurements, procedures, and conditions. For the purposes of this exercise, all were applied to the OBSERVATION domain. In some cases, it is clear that the data element belongs to another domain e.g. PSA levels are normally a laboratory measurement. For the classification of data elements, it may be necessary to consider additional factors such as the source of the data.

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Finding 3: The OHDSI tool, USAGI, proved an efficient tool for finding standard concepts that may match the data in the standard sets. Atlas/Athena is an alternative tool to identify related concepts.

Finding 4: The existence of standard set data in the standard vocabularies was patchy at all levels.

Finding 5: There are two principal methods of filling these gaps in the vocabulary. First, create new standard concepts for a specific use-case -using CONCEPT_IDS >2billion. These new concepts must be shipped with any data to facilitate analysis. The second method is to request from the vocabulary team that the missing concepts be included in a future release of the standard vocabulary. This has the advantage that these concepts will then be available to all researchers. For commonly used PROMS such as PROMIS, HAQ etc this would appear to be a sensible approach.

Finding 6: Executing the Data Analytics demonstrated how the EHDEN/OHDSI tools can be used to incorporate the key groups of ICHOM data elements into research questions i.e. baseline characteristics, diagnoses, treatments, and outcomes.

6. DISCUSSION

6.1 Mapping process

Mapping of ICHOM data set structures to the OMOP-CDM and the mapping of ICHOM data elements to the standard vocabulary was initiated in D2.2 and continued for inflammatory arthritis and prostate cancer in this deliverable. Identifying structural gaps to the OMOP-CDM structures (Objective 1) showed a high degree of compatibility between the standards. The prioritised standard sets consist primarily of simple data types such as numeric and text and unsurprisingly are accommodated in the OMOP-CDM. There is currently no facility for managing more complex data such as documents or images in the OMOP-CDM however, these did not arise here. A small number of the data elements directly match to fields in the OMOP-CDM even though, in some of these, variations exist between the standard sets.

A key feature in the OMOP-CDM is the existence of standard concepts. Mapping to these concepts in the OMOP-CDM accommodates the majority of the remaining standard set data elements. If no existing standard concept exists, a new concept can be created. Each standard concept belongs to a single domain, and the simplest implementation of an ICHOM standard set is to create new concepts for any missing elements in the observation domain. A more comprehensive approach is to ‘direct’ the data to its appropriate location in the OMOP-CDM by creating the new concepts in their natural domains e.g. a PSA value would exist in the measurement domain. Even though this is more complex, it facilitates other researchers’ reuse of the data because it is stored according to convention i.e. where it is expected to be.

The SURVEY_CONDUCT table is a key table for accommodating ICHOM’s standard sets in the OMOP-CDM. It facilitates administration of survey instances and ICHOM’s timing logic. The table has a specific field to hold the timing information e.g. ‘Baseline’ or ‘Annual Review’, and this information should be explicitly contained in datasets. While this timing sequence could also theoretically be deduced from the data dictionary, this is complex and error prone.

The method applied to the IA and LPCSS (Red path in Figure 14) was generalised and subsequently applied successfully to this phase of analysing the APCSS.

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Analysis continued, identifying gaps between the standard sets and the OMOP-CDM vocabulary (Objective 2). A generalised approach was necessary as detailed in Figure 9 and the red path in Figure 14. The OHDSI Usagi tool proved useful in this process by proposing mappings and creating outputs that could be used to incorporate mappings into an OMOP-CDM instance. However, it was clear that medical domain expertise from the ICHOM working groups and vocabulary expertise from OHDSI are necessary to achieve definitive mappings. Standard concepts are a fundamental building block in OHDSI and facilitate network analyses over multiple datasets standardised to the OMOP-CDM. Accordingly, matching standard set data elements to existing standard concepts in the OHDSI vocabulary is an important step to facilitate such analysis and benchmarking between institutions. Any concepts for which a match cannot be found in the existing standard vocabulary can be added to it. However, these new concepts must also be shipped with the dataset in order for them to have meaning in any subsequent analysis. Useful ideas to be applied in this exercise can be found here³⁶.

The timing of the vocabulary and working group teams involvement needs careful consideration to maximise efficiency. Access to teams should be via precise, specific questions. OHDSI forum discussions suggest that clear use-cases are a prerequisite to changes in the vocabulary i.e. while we are operating in this exploratory phase, local additions to the vocabulary are the correct approach. Other forum discussions suggest that widely used surveys should be added to the standard vocabularies when requested. It appears that working group representatives for ICHOM’s standard sets are generally available if needed.

When matching the ICHOM timing logic data to the OMOP-CDM, a gap in the underlying philosophies of the standards crystallised. OHDSI, by its definition, is analysing observational data whereas ICHOM’s philosophy is rooted in the measurement of standard outcomes i.e. if a standard set is in use then its data elements must be measured by the user -usually prospectively. Ideally, patients whose outcomes are being measured should have data collected at the intervals described in the timeline with patient-reported data collected at baseline and annually thereafter and clinical data collected at baseline and bi-annually thereafter. Its users and other stakeholders would ideally be in a position to implement this data collection as designed as presumably it corresponds with good clinical practice. However, even in prospective studies, it appears inevitable that there would be some loss of compliance with the timeline due to non-attendance, re-scheduling and other unexpected events and accordingly it is important that the degree of compliance required be further developed. This would also be applicable to retrospective studies such as those in OHDSI/EHDEN. For example, what is the tolerance on the 6-monthly and annual data collection events: Is 5-7 months good enough for 6-monthly? Is 10-14 months good enough for annual data? Does a missed data collection event automatically disqualify a patient from a study? Is compliance with this timeline a strict inclusion/exclusion criterion? If not what degree of compliance is required?

Furthermore, all ICHOM standard sets are not specific in their definition of the allowable source of data elements. These data elements could come from EHRs, claims data, surveys, or other systems. Accordingly, there may be situations where a data element is presented in a guise that is not in complete compliance with the standard set definition. ICHOM is cognisant of this gap and is in the process of developing guidance on best practice in this area.

Analysis continued by creating concept sets and cohort definitions in the Atlas environment. Cohort definition allowed specification of initial conditions, inclusion and exclusion criteria which could also facilitate incorporation of temporal logic into the cohort. This phase demonstrated how the key groups of ICHOM standard set data elements (baseline characteristics, clinical findings, outcomes etc) can be

³⁶ <https://forums.ohdsi.org/t/survey-data-mapping-question-and-response-pairs/6919>

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accessed in the vocabularies and incorporated into research questions. This step was theoretical in nature and as above, additional steps are needed for the required rigour to achieve acceptance by the IA or other standard set community. If mappings and research question design are to achieve acceptance, their development should be formalised and include medical expertise from the ICHOM standard set working group, vocabulary expertise, OMOP-CDM expertise as well as ICHOM/EHDEN input. Ideally, this would then be tested and implemented with real-world data.

6.2 Support for benchmarking data partners

Much of the EHDEN environment in which we are operating is exploratory – from finding data through to analysis/benchmarking. Many of the software tools we depend on are open source with a steep learning curve and without formal support. There are several distinct approaches to carrying out analyses in these environments and each comes with its own intricacies and idiosyncrasies, often not immediately obvious. Uncovering these is a time-consuming exercise. It is important that ICHOM & EHDEN understand the steep learning curve in mastering the ICHOM/EHDEN/OHDSI environment. Through establishing the pipelines for supporting the use of ICHOM standard sets, it is hoped this deliverable goes some way towards proposing a path for future applications. However, intended users of these pipelines need to be aware of this learning curve.

6.3 Improving the process of using ICHOM standard sets in EHDEN/OHDSI

Following from the above, some high-level matters arose that need stakeholder consideration:

- The development of the OMOP-CDM is a live project. Of particular interest to the ICHOM use-case is the recent introduction of the SURVEY_CONDUCT table. ICHOM could consider establishing a presence in the OHDSI forum to participate in the active discussions and influence future developments in the direction of their standard sets and outcomes measurement philosophy. This will require personnel with the requisite technical & analytics skills to engage with OHDSI and influence the development of the OMOP-CDM, the OHDSI tools, and the vocabularies to ensure that ICHOM’s requirements are incorporated into future designs and releases.

ICHOM’s presence in the forum could also guide the development of OMOP-CDM vocabularies which are refined and expanded regularly. ICHOM should engage with the OHDSI vocabulary team with a view to adding commonly used, ICHOM-recommended, data elements, PROM titles, questions and responses as standard concepts in subsequent releases of the standard vocabularies.

- Provision needs to be made for the support of all ICHOM standard sets and future sets in the EHDEN environment. A procedure is needed where ICHOM/EHDEN can access the working group representatives to verify semantics, and the translation of the sets into OMOP-CDM. The input of ICHOM personnel, experienced in the standard set development process, would be useful in establishing a pragmatic approach to this.

Proposed major steps in the mapping process for existing standard sets

- Creation of preliminary mappings by ICHOM/EHDEN personnel
- Discussion of mappings with the standard set working groups representatives
- Redrafting to incorporate working group knowledge
- Confirmation with vocabulary & OMOP-CDM team
- Testing with synthetic and real-world data

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- The co-existence of ICHOM’s primarily ‘prospective’ focus and the realities of OHDSI’s ‘observational’ data is an important matter. If the standard sets are to be fully implemented in this environment, guidance around the potential sources of valid observational data is required. ICHOM is cognisant of this gap and will work to close this. In particular guidance on the use of EHR and administrative data would be valuable as would tolerances around the standard set definitions and their temporal logic. Some flexibility in data quality here may have the welcome side effect of persuading data owners to adopt the standard sets.

Some of the challenges of using observational data for benchmarking according to ICHOM standards have been discussed above. Alternatives to forcing observational datasets to ICHOM standards need exploration. The existing ICHOM GLOBE benchmarking work was considered as part of this research. It offers some guidelines that will be useful in future benchmarking in the EHDEN project.

Acknowledging some overlap with the above points, more technical matters are listed below:

- It would significantly simplify the ETL process to know the timing of the survey in the standard set sequence e.g. is it a ‘Baseline’ or ‘Annual Review’ etc? By including the date that the survey was conducted and its place in the ICHOM standard set logic e.g. ‘Baseline’ ‘Annual review’ etc. These fields should be added to the data sets if not already there.

Fields in the data dictionary intending to hold multiple values e.g. IA diagnoses in the IASS, are problematic. Replacing these with Y/N fields indicating the presence of the disease resolves this. Date of first diagnosis for each positive answer could also be included.

- There are many minor discussions to be had with the OHDSI and vocabulary teams. E.g. Is the method used for creating concept sets for ICHOM standard set conditions correct? Would it be better to have a single concept set for the 4 inflammatory arthritis conditions? Is there a better or more efficient method? How does the ‘Optimise’ function work? It seems to look for concepts in the ‘Concept Set Expression’ that are already included as ‘Included Concepts’ and proposes their removal. Should this be done, reviewed, and as-a-rule accepted? Should known treatments for the conditions have been included? Should known drugs for the conditions have been included? How can these decisions be reviewed by a domain expert? etc. These and other questions might be addressed in a formal mapping process involving the OHDSI vocabulary team, the OMOP-CDM team along with the ICHOM working group.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The mapping process for the prioritised standard sets to the CDM structures worked well – including the accommodation of timing logic and care-pathways. However, it is possible that other standard sets and real-world applications will bring new issues to light.

The coverage of the standard sets in the CDM standard vocabularies was found to be patchy and this is likely to be a continuing issue with real-world datasets (RWD). The expansion of the standard vocabulary needs consideration. Should commonly used PROMs be in the standard vocabularies? Should the mappings primary aim be to accommodate benchmarking, or should the mappings support the deeper EHDEN-adopted ‘FAIR’³⁷ philosophy?

³⁷ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4792175/>

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There are several areas requiring further cooperation between the stakeholders to optimise use of ICHOM’s standard sets for benchmarking in the EHDEN environment including clarification of the allowable sources of data, tolerances, benchmarking guideline, general mapping processes, and technical usage of the OMOP-CDM.

The outputs from this exercise will be enriched by application to RWD and this will bring its own unique issues, particularly data quality and provenance.

7.1 Recommended future work in EHDEN

- Develop opportunities for application of these techniques to real-world datasets. There are current opportunities in Hasselt University, Belgium and Erasmus MC, Rotterdam with ICHOM users wishing to execute benchmarking within the EHDEN project. An initial approach to this work is introduced in Appendix G.
- ICHOM/EHDEN could evaluate the potential for an ICHOM-a-thon to initiate a bridge between EHDEN and ICHOM end-users. This will provide a practical platform for using the pipelines developed here and extending them to real-world data.
- Code development to automate the analysis and ETL processes in the EHDEN environment.
- Expansion of the techniques to other ICHOM standard sets.
- Integration with other EHDEN work packages for use-cases and experience-exchange e.g. ICHOM can engage with WP5 and provide feedback on the experiences of this use-case utilising the toolset to implement outcomes-based research.

APPENDIX A - APPLYING THE OMOP COMMON DATA MODEL TO SURVEY DATA

Applying the OMOP Common Data Model to Survey Data

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ABSTRACT

Background: The Epidemiology Analytics group at Janssen R&D has successfully transformed the NHANES dataset into the OMOP CDM and this study will examine the methods used to achieve this transformation.

Objectives: Evaluate the feasibility of transforming survey data into CDM.

Methods: NHANES variables were loaded into the OHDSI tool Usagi and mappings were created to link the survey questions to standard concepts. These maps are added to the SOURCE_TO_CONCEPT_MAP table which facilitates the transformation.

Results: There was 100% match between the raw data and transformed data break outs.

Conclusions: Survey data is feasible to transform into the CDM as illustrated with NHANES with no information loss from the source and our experience leads us to recommend that a similar process can be followed for other question/response observational data sources, including other surveys and registries.

Table 2: As reported by NHANES, the raw data breakout showing the frequency of each response to the 2005-2006 Mental Health Depression Screener question DPQ020¹.

DPQ020 Response Frequency			
Code or Value	Value Description	Count	Cumulative
0	Not at all	3,769	3,769
1	Several days	769	4,538
2	More than half the days	179	4,717
3	Nearly every day	114	4,831
9	Don't know	5	4,836
.	Missing	498	5,334

Step 1: NHANES Mental Health Depression Screener data loaded. SEQN represents a unique patient identifier and each column represents a survey question. In the below example person 31214 responded to question DPQ020 with a three, which in this instance means "Nearly every day".

SEQN	DPQ010	DPQ020	DPQ030	DPQ040	DPQ050	DPQ060	DPQ070	DPQ080	DPQ090	DPQ100
31214		3	1	2	2	2	2	0	0	1

SEQN	Source Code	Source Value
31214	DPQ010	2
31214	DPQ020	3
31214	DPQ030	1
31214	DPQ040	2
31214	DPQ050	2
31214	DPQ060	2
31214	DPQ070	2
31214	DPQ080	0
31214	DPQ090	0
31214	DPQ100	1

Step 2: Source data are pivoted so that each row represents one unique response. The question identifier is now housed in the "Source Code" column and the patient's answers are housed in the "Source Value" column.

Source Code	Source Value
DPQ010	2
DPQ020	3
DPQ030	1
DPQ040	2
DPQ050	2
DPQ060	2
DPQ070	2
DPQ080	0
DPQ090	0
DPQ100	1

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Margaret Blacketer, Erica Voss, and Patrick Ryan are full time employees of Janssen Research and Development, a unit of Johnson and Johnson. The work on this study was part of their employment. They also hold pension rights from the company and own stock and stock options.

BACKGROUND

- The Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) Common Data Model (CDM) has been shown to be an effective way to standardize observational health databases but has not been as commonly applied to survey and registry databases as it has for electronic health records and administrative claims^{1-3,6}.
- The National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES) is a program that combines survey information and physical examination results to determine the prevalence of major diseases and risk factors for disease among the U.S. population⁴.
- The NHANES dataset has been successfully transformed into the OMOP CDM and this study will examine the methods used to achieve this transformation and serve as a guide on how to approach the conversion of survey and registry data to the OMOP CDM with little to no loss of data integrity.

OBJECTIVES

- Evaluate the feasibility of transforming survey data into CDM.
- Assess the completeness of vocabulary mapping for survey questions and responses into standardized vocabularies.

METHODS

- We will evaluate the feasibility of survey extract, transform, load (ETL) through examination of our ETL for the NHANES dataset, which is a national open source database comprised largely of data in the form of question/response pairs.
- We chose to focus on the 2005-2006 Mental Health Depression Screener because each participant aged 18 years and older was an eligible respondent, allowing for a robust set of answers (question DPQ020 will be highlighted throughout as an example of how both a question and response are translated into the CDM).
- We designed an ETL process for survey questionnaires in columnar format (each question is a field, each response is a record) into the entity, attribute, value (EAV) structure of the OBSERVATION table within CDM (each record has two fields, one for question, one for response); we applied this ETL process to all questions in NHANES to assess if the process was suitable to accommodate all types of questions posed in the survey.
- We determined the questions and responses from the source and used Usagi⁵ to evaluate with a defined threshold of 0.6 and then examined what percent of questions we were able to map to a standardized vocabulary. Table 1 shows how the Mental Health Depression Screener questions were successfully mapped to Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes (LOINC) concepts.

Table 1: NHANES Mental Health Depression Screener Questions Mapped to LOINC Concepts using Usagi

Source Code	Source Description*	Target Concept ID	Concept Name
DPQ010	Little interest or pleasure in doing things?	3042924	Little interest or pleasure in doing things; in last 2 weeks [Reported.PHQ]
DPQ020	Feeling down, depressed or hopeless?	4075792	Feeling or appearing down, depressed, or hopeless in last 2 weeks; frequency [Observed PHQ-9 MDSv3]
DPQ030	Trouble falling or staying asleep, or sleeping too much?	3045933	Trouble falling or staying asleep, or sleeping too much in last 2 weeks [Reported.PHQ]
DPQ040	Feeling tired or having little energy?	42870477	I feel tired - have no energy in the last 2 weeks or more [M3]
DPQ050	Poor appetite or overeating?	3044098	Poor appetite or overeating in last 2 weeks [Reported.PHQ]
DPQ060	Feeling bad about yourself - or that you are a failure or have let yourself or your family down?	3043801	Feeling bad about yourself - or that you are a failure or have let yourself or your family down in last 2 weeks [Reported.PHQ]
DPQ070	Trouble concentrating on things, such as reading the newspaper or watching television?	3045019	Trouble concentrating on things, such as reading the newspaper or watching television in last 2 weeks [Reported.PHQ]
DPQ080	Moving or speaking so slowly that other people could have noticed? Or the opposite - being so fidgety or restless that you have been moving around a lot more than usual?	3043785	Moving or speaking so slowly that other people could have noticed. Or the opposite - being so fidgety or restless that you have been moving around a lot more than usual in last 2 weeks [Reported.PHQ]
DPQ090	Thoughts that you would be better off dead or of hurting yourself in some way?	3043462	Thoughts that you would be better off dead, or of hurting yourself in some way in last 2 weeks [Reported.PHQ]
DPQ100	How difficult have these problems made it for you to do your work, take care of things at home, or get along with people?	40772146	How difficult have these made it for you to do your work, take care of things at home, or get along with other people [Reported.PHQ]

*Each question was asked in relation to the past 2 weeks.

PERSON_ID	OBSERVATION_CONCEPT_ID	...	VALUE_AS_NUMBER	VALUE_AS_STRING	VALUE_AS_CONCEPT_ID	OBSERVATION_SOURCE_VALUE
31214	3042924	...	2	More than half the days	45878994	DPQ010
31214	4075792	...	3	Nearly every day	45882010	DPQ020
31214	3045933	...	1	Several days	45879886	DPQ030
31214	42870477	...	2	More than half the days	45878994	DPQ040
31214	3044098	...	2	More than half the days	45878994	DPQ050
31214	3043801	...	2	More than half the days	45878994	DPQ060
31214	3045019	...	2	More than half the days	45878994	DPQ070
31214	3043785	...	0	Not at all	45883172	DPQ080
31214	3043462	...	0	Not at all	45883172	DPQ090
31214	40772146	...	1	Somewhat difficult	45877108	DPQ100

Step 3: The SOURCE_TO_CONCEPT_MAP table is used to map the questions and answers into the OBSERVATION table. In this instance the OBSERVATION table is the destination because the framework of the table allows for the storage of both the question and answer as concepts while also allowing the question identifier (OBSERVATION_SOURCE_VALUE) to be captured.

RESULTS

- From the source data we use 2,939 questions across 71,916 respondents. We were able to transform 100% source data question/answer pairs to the CDM. Of the questions, 366 were previously manually mapped to standard concepts on manual review and 125 were confirmed with Usagi. Using Usagi with an automated threshold of 0.6 achieved another 543 mappings for a total of 668.
- There was 100% match between the raw data and transformed data break outs. The NHANES website lists 5,334 cumulative responses to question DPQ020 and after transformation there are 5,334 rows of data in the OBSERVATION table with an OBSERVATION_SOURCE_VALUE of DPQ020¹.

CONCLUSIONS

- Survey data is feasible to transform into the CDM as illustrated with NHANES with no information loss from the source.
- Vocabulary mapping is going to be incomplete due to the unstructured nature of the question/response pairs and it will not be solved by manual or automated mapping tools since many of the questions asked in surveys do not have standard concepts.
- The structure of the OBSERVATION table can hold all question/response pairs but more work needs to be done to determine if a particular question generates data that best belongs in a different domain (e.g. self-reported HbA1c lab values may be better stored in the MEASUREMENT table) but we currently do not have a fully automated process to handle those decisions.
- Nonetheless, our experience leads us to recommend that a similar process can be followed for other question/response observational data sources, including other surveys and registries.

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APPENDIX B - DRAFT MAPPING OF INFLAMMATORY ARTHRITIS STANDARD SET TO THE STANDARD VOCABULARY

sourceCode	sourceName	targetConceptId	targetConceptName	targetVocab	targetDomain
N/A	Patient ID	0	Unmapped		
AGE	Age	4265453	Age	SNOMED	Observation
SEX	Sex at birth	46235213	Sex assigned at birth	LOINC	Observation
SOCIO	Education level	46238019	Education	LOINC	Meas Value
SMOKING	Smoking status	4203874	Smoking monitoring status	SNOMED	Observation
BASEHBP	High blood pressure	40761396	Ever told by doctor or nurse that you have high blood pressure	LOINC	Observation
BASEAMI	Myocardial infarction	4163874	History of myocardial infarction	SNOMED	Observation
BASESTR	Stroke (excluding transient ischemic attacks)	4077982	History of cerebrovascular accident	SNOMED	Observation
BASEOHD	Other heart disease	45879053	Other heart disease	LOINC	Meas Value
BASECLD	Chronic lung disease	4188164	History of chronic lung disease	SNOMED	Observation
BASEDM	Diabetes mellitus	4058709	H/O: diabetes mellitus	SNOMED	Observation
BASEMALIG	Malignancies	4312326	Neoplasm, malignant	SNOMED	Observation
BASEDEP	Depression	4059192	H/O: depression	SNOMED	Observation
BASEFRAC	Fracture	4193155	H/O: fracture	SNOMED	Observation
BASEULCER	Stomach ulcer	4265600	Gastric ulcer	SNOMED	Condition
BASESTOM	Stomach problem	4113551	Stomach problem	SNOMED	Condition
BASEOB	Obesity	4059799	H/O: obesity	SNOMED	Observation
IA_DIAG	Inflammatory arthritis diagnosis	4291025	Arthritis	SNOMED	Condition
RA_DIAG	Rheumatoid arthritis diagnosis	80809	Rheumatoid arthritis	SNOMED	Condition
PA_DIAG	Psoriatic arthritis diagnosis	40319772	Psoriatic arthritis	SNOMED	Condition
AS_DIAG	Ankylosing spondylitis diagnosis	437082	Ankylosing spondylitis	SNOMED	Condition
JIA_DIAG	Juvenile idiopathic arthritis diagnosis	4259507	Juvenile idiopathic arthritis	SNOMED	Condition
DISDUR	Disease duration	4160852	Date of diagnosis	SNOMED	Observation

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IMM_RF	Rheumatoid factor	37397812	Rheumatoid factor	SNOMED	Observation
IMM_ACPA	ACPA	36676230	Anti-cyclic citrullinated peptide antibody positive	SNOMED	Condition
PROMCHOICE_PAIN	PROM Choice - Pain	0	Unmapped		
PAIN_NRS	Pain Numerical Rating Scale	43055141	Pain severity - 0-10 verbal numeric rating [Score] - Reported	LOINC	Measurement
PROMCHOICE_FAT	PROM Choice - Fatigue	0	Unmapped		
FATIGUE_NRS	Fatigue Numerical Rating Scale	4260261	Level of fatigue	SNOMED	Observation
PROMCHOICE_ACT	PROM Choice - Activity limitations	0	Unmapped		
HAQ2_Q01	HAQ-II Question 1	46235688	Total score [HAQII]	LOINC	Observation
HAQ2_Q02 -10	HAQ-II Question 2 -10	0	Unmapped		
PROMCHOICE_OEPHI	PROM Choice - Overall Emotional and Physical Health Impact	0	Unmapped		
OEPHI_NRS	Overall Emotional and Physical Health Impact Numerical Rating Scale	4150298	Numerical range	SNOMED	Observation
PROMCHOICE_WSHAP	PROM Choice - Work/school/housework ability and productivity	0	Unmapped		
WPAI_GH_Q01 -6	Work Productivity and Activity Impairment Questionnaire: General Health V2.0 (WPAI:GH) Question 1-6	0	Unmapped		
SAE	Serious Adverse Events	45884383	Adverse event	LOINC	Meas Value
SAE_TYPE	Serious Adverse Events - Classification	0	Unmapped		
REM_LDA_TARG	Disease activity target	0	Unmapped		
REM_LDA_REAC	Disease activity target reached	0	Unmapped		
IDA	Inflammatory disease activity	0	Unmapped		
IDA_RES	Inflammatory disease activity result	35621962	DAS - Disease Activity Score	SNOMED	Observation

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APPENDIX C - DRAFT MAPPING OF LOCALISED PROSTATE CANCER STANDARD SET TO THE STANDARD VOCABULARY

sourceCode	sourceName	targetConceptId	targetConceptName	targetVocab	targetDomain
N/A	Patient ID	0	Unmapped		
Age	Age (Date of Birth)	4083587	Date of birth	SNOMED	Observation
COMORB	Comorbidities	0	Unmapped		
DIAGDATE	Date of histological diagnosis	40766651	Date of diagnosis	LOINC	Observation
PSA	Most recent PSA value before histological diagnosis	4272032	Prostate specific antigen measurement	SNOMED	Measurement
TNMCT	Clinical tumor stage	4161178	Tumor stage	SNOMED	Observation
TNMCN	Clinical nodal stage	0	Unmapped		
BIOPCORE	Number of biopsy cores taken	4078191	Number of biopsies	SNOMED	Observation
BIOPPOS	Number of biopsy cores positive	4269746	Number of tissue cores positive for carcinoma	SNOMED	Observation
BIOPINVOL	Greatest percentage involvement	0	Unmapped		
GLEASONBIOP1	Gleason score: Primary	4293445	Primary Gleason pattern	SNOMED	Observation
GLEASONBIOP2	Gleason score: Secondary	4297948	Secondary Gleason pattern	SNOMED	Observation
TNMPT	Pathological tumor stage	4161178	Tumor stage	SNOMED	Observation
TNMPN	Pathological nodal stage	0	Unmapped		
MARGIN	Margin status	4157482	Tumor margin status	SNOMED	Observation
MARGINFOC	Margin status focality	4157482	Tumor margin status	SNOMED	Observation
GLEASONPATH1	Pathological Gleason grade: Primary	4293445	Primary Gleason pattern	SNOMED	Observation
GLEASONPATH2	Pathological Gleason grade: Secondary	4297948	Secondary Gleason pattern	SNOMED	Observation
PRIMARYTX	Treatment modalities used	0	Unmapped		
PRIMARYTXFT	Type of focal therapy	0	Unmapped		
PRWATCHDATE	Date watchful waiting initiated	0	Unmapped		
PRACTIVEDATE	Date active surveillance initiated	0	Unmapped		
PRRADPROTXDATE	Date of primary radical prostatectomy	0	Unmapped		

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PRNERVESPARE	Primary nerve sparing status	0	Unmapped		
PREBRTTODDOSE	Primary external Beam Radiation Therapy: Dose (Gray)	4036405	Teletherapy radiation dose specification	SNOMED	Observation
PREBRTDOSEPERFRACT	Primary external Beam Radiation Therapy: Average dose per fraction (Gray)	4036742	Teletherapy dose rate	SNOMED	Observation
PREBRTTXSTARTDATE	Start date of primary external beam radiation therapy	0	Unmapped		
PREBRTTXSTOPDATE	Stop date of primary external beam radiation therapy	0	Unmapped		
PREBRTTXONGOING	Ongoing primary external beam radiation therapy	4141448	Teleradiotherapy procedure	SNOMED	Procedure
PRBRACHYTXSTARTDATE	Start date of primary brachytherapy	40766656	Start date of treatment or therapy	LOINC	Observation
PRBRACHYTXSTOPDATE	Stop date of primary brachytherapy	40766659	End date of treatment or therapy	LOINC	Observation
PRBRACHYTXONGOING	Ongoing primary brachytherapy	40317890	Brachytherapy	SNOMED	Procedure
PRBRACHYDOSERATE	Primary brachytherapy dose	4172376	Brachytherapy dose rate	SNOMED	Observation
PRADTTXSTARTDATE	Start date of primary androgen deprivation therapy	0	Unmapped		
PRADTTXSTOPDATE	Stop date of primary androgen deprivation therapy	0	Unmapped		
PRADTTXONGOING	Ongoing primary androgen deprivation therapy	45768763	Androgen deprivation therapy	SNOMED	Procedure
PRFOCTXSTARTDATE	Start date of primary focal therapy	0	Unmapped		
PRFOCTXSTOPDATE	Stop date of primary focal therapy	0	Unmapped		
PRFOCTXONGOING	Ongoing primary focal therapy	0	Unmapped		
PRIMARYTXOTHER	Primary treatment modality other than those explicitly listed	0	Unmapped		
PROHERTXSTARTDATE	Start date of other primary therapy	40766656	Start date of treatment or therapy	LOINC	Observation
PROHERTXSTOPDATE	Stop date of other primary therapy	40766659	End date of treatment or therapy	LOINC	Observation
PROHERTXONGOING	Ongoing other therapy	0	Unmapped		
SALVAGETXINI	Salvage treatment initiated (within last year?)	4107456	Salvage procedure	SNOMED	Observation
SALVAGETX	Salvage treatment modalities used	0	Unmapped		

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SALVAGETXOTHER	Salvage treatment modality other than those explicitly listed	0	Unmapped		
SVRADPROTXDATE	Date of radical prostatectomy	0	Unmapped		
SVNERVESPARE	Nerve sparing status	0	Unmapped		
SVEBRTTODDOSE	External Beam Radiation Therapy: Dose (Gray)	4036742	Teletherapy dose rate	SNOMED	Observation
SVEBRTDOSEPERFRACT	External Beam Radiation Therapy: Average dose per fraction (Gray)	0	Unmapped		
SVEBRTTXSTARTDATE	Start date of external beam radiation therapy	0	Unmapped		
SVEBRTTXSTOPDATE	Stop date of external beam radiation therapy	0	Unmapped		
SVEBRTTXONGOING	Ongoing external beam radiation therapy	46270546	History of external beam radiation therapy	SNOMED	Observation
SVBRACHYTXSTARTDATE	Start date of brachytherapy	0	Unmapped		
SVBRACHYTXSTOPDATE	Stop date of brachytherapy	0	Unmapped		
SVBRACHYTXONGOING	Ongoing brachytherapy	40317890	Brachytherapy	SNOMED	Procedure
SVBRACHYDOSERATE	Brachytherapy dose	4172376	Brachytherapy dose rate	SNOMED	Observation
SVADTTXSTARTDATE	Start date of androgen deprivation therapy	0	Unmapped		
SVADTTXSTOPDATE	Stop date of androgen deprivation therapy	0	Unmapped		
SVADTTXONGOING	Ongoing androgen deprivation therapy	45768763	Androgen deprivation therapy	SNOMED	Procedure
SVFOCTXSTARTDATE	Start date of focal therapy	0	Unmapped		
SVFOCTXSTOPDATE	Stop date of focal therapy	0	Unmapped		
SVFOCTXONGOING	Ongoing focal therapy	0	Unmapped		
SVOTHERTXSTARTDATE	Start date of other therapy	40766656	Start date of treatment or therapy	LOINC	Observation
SVOTHERTXSTOPDATE	Stop date of other therapy	0	Unmapped		
SVOTHERTXONGOING	Ongoing other therapy	0	Unmapped		
COMPLSURG	Clavien complication (max grade)	0	Unmapped		
COMPLRAD	CTCAE grade 3 or 4 complication during treatment or within 6 months after completing treatment	763791	Common terminology criteria for adverse events grade 3	SNOMED	Condition

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COMPLRADDOMGRA	CTCAE domain and grade	763789	National Cancer Institute common terminology criteria for adverse event grade finding	SNOMED	Condition
COMPLRADDOMOTHER	CTCAE domain other than those explicitly listed	46272971	Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events	SNOMED	Measurement
EPIC26_Q01 – q26	Question 1 -26 of EPIC-26*	0	Unmapped		
LIBID_Q01 -3e	Question 1-3e of Utilization of Sexual Medications/Devices	0	Unmapped		
DEATH	Death: Patient died	45878200	Patient died	LOINC	Meas Value
DEATHDATE	Death: Date of death	21494750	Date of death [Date]	LOINC	Observation
DEATHLPC	Cause of death: Death attributable to localized prostate cancer	45880469	Cause of Death	LOINC	Meas Value
METADEV	Disease control: Metastasis	432851	Secondary malignant neoplastic disease	SNOMED	Condition
METADATE	Disease control: Date metastasis identified	0	Unmapped		
BIOCHEM	Disease control: Biochemical recurrence	37208188	Non-metastatic prostate cancer	SNOMED	Condition
BIOCHEMDATE	Disease control: Date biochemical recurrence identified	32529	Disease Recurrence	Episode	Episode
BIOCHEMPSA	Disease control: Biochemical recurrence PSA value	0	Unmapped		

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APPENDIX D - THE OBSERVATION TABLE

Field	Req.	Type	Description	Source/Explanation
observation_id	Yes	integer	A unique identifier for each observation.	Generate on insert.
person_id	Yes	integer	A foreign key identifier to the Person about whom the observation was recorded. The demographic details of that Person are stored in the PERSON table.	From source data or pseudonymised
observation_concept_id	Yes	integer	A foreign key to the standard observation concept identifier in the Standardized Vocabularies.	Link from source data to Source_to_concept_Map table e.g. this is the concept_id for the specific HAQII question.
observation_date	No	date	The date of the observation.	Date of PROM
observation_datetime	Yes	datetime	The date and time of the observation.	Date of PROM
observation_type_concept_id	Yes	integer	A foreign key to the predefined concept identifier in the Standardized Vocabularies reflecting the type of the observation.	This should contain the concept_id for 'observation recorded from a survey' 45905771
value_as_number	No	float	The observation result stored as a number. This is applicable to observations where the result is expressed as a numeric value.	From source data
value_as_string	No	varchar(60)	The observation result stored as a string. This is applicable to observations where the result is expressed as verbatim text.	From source data
value_as_concept_id	No	Integer	A foreign key to an observation result stored as a Concept ID. This is applicable to observations where the result can be expressed as a Standard Concept from the Standardized Vocabularies (e.g., positive/negative, present/absent, low/high, etc.).	Link from source data to Source_to_concept_Map table
qualifier_concept_id	No	integer	A foreign key to a Standard Concept ID for a qualifier (e.g., severity of drug-drug interaction alert)	N/A
unit_concept_id	No	integer	A foreign key to a Standard Concept ID of measurement units in the Standardized Vocabularies.	N/A
provider_id	No	integer	A foreign key to the provider in the PROVIDER table who was responsible for making the observation.	Generate on insert? Might be useful – leave for now
visit_occurrence_id	No	integer	A foreign key to the visit in the VISIT_OCCURRENCE table during which the observation was recorded.	Might be useful – leave out for now
visit_detail_id	No	integer	A foreign key to the visit in the VISIT_DETAIL table during which the observation was recorded.	N/A

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observation_source_value	No	varchar(50)	The observation code as it appears in the source data. This code is mapped to a Standard Concept in the Standardized Vocabularies and the original code is, stored here for reference.	Source data (this is in the Answers field in the testable)
observation_source_concept_id	Yes	integer	A foreign key to a Concept that refers to the code used in the source.	Link from source data to Source_to_concept_Map table because the source concept might not be a standard concept
unit_source_value	No	varchar(50)	The source code for the unit as it appears in the source data. This code is mapped to a standard unit concept in the Standardized Vocabularies and the original code is, stored here for reference.	N/A
qualifier_source_value	No	varchar(50)	The source value associated with a qualifier to characterize the observation	N/A
observation_event_id	No	integer	A foreign key to an event table (e.g., PROCEDURE_OCCURRENCE_ID).	Might be useful – leave out for now
obs_event_field_concept_id	Yes	integer	A foreign key that refers to a Standard Concept identifier in the Standardized Vocabularies referring to the field represented in the OBSERVATION_EVENT_ID.	N/A
value_as_datetime	No	datetime	The observation result stored as a datetime value. This is applicable to observations where the result is expressed as a point in time.	N/A

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APPENDIX E - WHICH IASS RECOMMENDED PROMS ARE ALREADY IN THE OHDSI STANDARD VOCABULARY?

Some PROM instruments exist as entries in the CONCEPT table and have a DOMAIN_ID of 'Measurement'. An assessment of a person using this instrument also has an entry in the CONCEPT table with a DOMAIN_ID of 'Procedure'. Some of the instruments also have their component questions in the CONCEPT table with a DOMAIN_ID of 'Observation'.

An overall score for an instrument can exist in the CONCEPT table also with a DOMAIN_ID of 'Observation'.

For Inflammatory Arthritis, QUERY 1 below discovers 5 possible entries in the CONCEPT table relating to the recommended PROM instruments. Of these, only 'BASFI'³⁸ accurately reflects the standard set name. However, none of the 10 questions³⁹ constituting the BASFI are present in the CONCEPT table in this version of the OHDSI vocabulary (see QUERY 2).

A variation (youth version) on the IASS recommended PROM EQ-5D-5L is present as an instrument in the concept table – although apparently duplicated. Additionally, constituent questions are also present in the table and a procedure for assessment using the instrument are present in the CONCEPT table.

A general search for terms 'like' the names of the instruments recommended in the IASS yields a result set of 77 related concepts principally involving the HAQ, HAQII, PROMIS, FACIT-F, and EQ-5D-Y

Domain	Survey	Answer Type	ATLAS/ATHENA Exact match /nearly match
Pain	Numerical rating scale	Numerical	n/a
	Visual analogue scale	Converted to numerical i.e. Likert	n/a
	SF-36 bodily pain ⁴⁰	Converted to numerical	0/4
	RAND bodily pain	Converted to numerical	2
	PROMIS pain interference ⁴¹	Converted to numerical	2/2602
	PedsQL 3.0 Arthritis module pain and hurt	Converted to numerical	0
Fatigue	FACIT-F	Converted to numerical	4/1000+
	BRAF-MDQ	Numeric, convert to numeric and 'Less than an hour', 'all day', 'several hours'	0
	PROMIS fatigue	Converted to numerical	1
	PedsQL4.0 SF 15 Generic Core Scales Fatigue	Converted to numerical	0
Activity Limitation	HAQ-II	Conversion to numeric.	0/455
	HAQ-DI	Conversion to numeric. Use of devices or aids may be in CONCEPTS. Categories of help also. Yes/No.	1/455
	MD-HAQ	Conversion to numeric.	0/455

³⁸ Bath Ankylosing Spondylitis Functional Index

³⁹ <http://basdai.com/BASFI.php>

⁴⁰

<https://dictionary.fitbir.nih.gov/portal/publicData/dataElementAction!view.action?dataElementName=SF36BodyPainScore&publicArea=true>

⁴¹ http://www.healthmeasures.net/index.php?option=com_instruments&view=measure&id=164&Itemid=992

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	PROMIS Physical Function	Conversion to numeric.	4/2602
	BASFI	numeric	1
	C-HAQ	Conversion to numeric.	0/455
Overall emotional and physical health impact	JAMAR	?	0/10
	EQ-5D-5L	Conversion to numeric.	0/13
	SF-6D	Subset of SF-36	0/4
	RAID	numeric	0
	PSAID	numeric	0
	CIHQ	?	0
Work/school/housework ability and productivity	WPAI	Y/N, Numeric	0
	PedsQL4.0 SF 15 Generic Core Scales School Functioning	Converted to numerical	0

Table: IASS recommended PROMS, data types and presence in the standard vocabularies.

APPENDIX F - SURVEYS IN THE OMOP-CDM V5.x

The SURVEY_CONDUCT table was introduced in the OMOP-CDM V6. Most of the Atlas tools are currently designed to work with the OMOP-CDM V5.x. There are a couple of possibilities that can be explored to assess the functionality of V5 in this regard.

- In the absence of the SURVEY_CONDUCT table, could the other relationships as described above be maintained? If one considers the SURVEY_CONDUCT table to be a ‘master’ table for an instance of a questionnaire, is there a way to maintain a link to the ‘child’ records. This has been explored with some success in earlier work (See Appendix A).
- Concepts could be created representing the temporal event e.g. ‘Baseline’, ‘Annual Review’
- Inclusion/Exclusion criteria in Cohort creation could also be considered.
- Custom code (SQL/Python) can also be considered
- Can a SURVEY_CONDUCT table simply be added to the V5.x database instance?

APPENDIX G - FUTURE WORK: REAL-WORLD DATA

This work was carried out using simulated data. This was a necessary first step to gain familiarity with the marriage of the ICHOM and OHDSI standards - a prerequisite to engaging with institutions using real world data (RWD). The use of RWD will bring new challenges to the ETL process. When dealing with RWD and the ultimate goal of using ICHOM’s standard sets for benchmarking between institutions, there are a couple of data scenarios to consider.

Scenario 1: The institution has a dedicated ICHOM Standard Set only, and the intention is to benchmark against other institutions with similar data. This approach will follow a path similar to that followed with the simulated data. A key step will then be to establish the degree of data integrity maintained through the conversion process. Standard and customised analytics can then be applied for benchmarking purposes. There are a couple of risks with this approach. If this approach unquestioningly accepts the semantic equivalence of the data and the quality of the data from the benchmarking institutions, the benchmarking may not be comparing like with like.

Scenario 2: Alternatively, the data available from the institution is more general observational data from a combination of EHRs, Claims and administrative sources, and perhaps questionnaires. In this case, the data’s structure, provenance, and quality require quality assessment and to see if the minimum required data is

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present. This scenario also needs to consider acceptable tolerances around ICHOM’s timing logic. As shown in Figure 2, the data collection timeline from the IASS Reference Guide requires that data be collected at specific intervals. Although this is presumably based on a clinical requirement, it appears unlikely that this will be strictly adhered to, in particular in observational data. For this reason, tolerances around this element need to be clarified. Alternatively, there is potential to achieve some of this logic in the cohort definition phase in Atlas through initial conditions, inclusion and exclusion criteria. Other machine learning techniques such as Process Mining might give similar insights in the analysis phase.

In both of the above scenarios, if the pragmatic and expeditious approach to mapping the data sets to the OMOP-CDM is achieved by simply creating new standard concepts to represent the data elements rather than seeking to map as many as possible to existing standard concepts, then the value of the process to the wider networked research community is possibly reduced as the data will be difficult to find. This is not ideal given EHDEN’s commitment to the FAIR⁴² principles.

To avoid some of these issues, in both of the above scenarios, a number of questions arise for each data element:

- What is the data source? EHR, claims, administrative data, physician or patient reported?
- Was the data contemporaneously recorded?
- How old is the information?
- Is it an observation, a measurement, a procedure, a condition?
- What OMOP-CDM table should it be stored in?
- Is it a standard concept?

Where a real-world dataset is available, the ETL process is clearly different. First, matching the structures of the source data and the OMOP-CDM is addressed. The OHDSI toolset includes several tools to assist in this ETL process. ‘White Rabbit’ scans the source data structure producing a report of the tables, fields, and contents to assist in the ETL process. The report acts as an input into ‘Rabbit in a hat’ which produces an initial ETL design. This ETL design proposes a mapping between tables and fields in the source data and corresponding fields in the OMOP-CDM. It does not produce code required for the ETL process, rather a proposed mapping on which code can be based.

Figure 21: RWD ETL 1

‘Usagi’ assists in the mapping of the contents to the preloaded ‘Vocabulary’ in the OMOP-CDM. It scans the source data content and provides suggested mappings of the content to Standard Concepts in the ‘Vocabulary’. The results are then appended to the already existing mappings table (source_to_concept_map) and a metadata entry to the vocabulary table is also recommended.

Figure 22: RWD ETL 2

⁴² <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4792175/>

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The ETL process is normally followed by a test and quality control step. ETL can be an onerous process, requiring data experts, OMOP-CDM expertise, medical knowledge, technical expertise.

It should be noted that there have been several attempts to create a one-size-fits-all ETL tool in the OHDSI environment, but this has not proved successful due to the unique designs of the source data bases. Therefore, a significant level of expertise is required for ETL to be successful. Expert experience with the source data is a prerequisite as is technical expertise around coding systems and the technical aspects of ETL coding. Some of the issues requiring ongoing expertise include: incorporation of changes in the source data with time, new data quality control scenarios, ETL code bugs, new vocabularies, and OMOP-CDM updates. Additional chapters on data quality, clinical validity, software validity, and method are included in the Book of OHDSI⁴³. The OHDSI fora provide additional support for partners in the ETL process⁴⁴.

Unknown provenance of real-world data

The provenance of the actual data itself also requires consideration:

What is the source of the data? i.e. EHR, EHR +Survey, Claims etc. What are the implications of this? There are active discussions in the EHDEN forums on the handling of data from disparate sources. REDCap is a survey instrument and has generated such discussions and suggestions that would have standard set data not necessarily treated as a survey but rather as a legitimate source system following all the normal conventions of mapping and ETL – particularly if the ‘survey’ incorporates pulls from EHRs or Claims data.

Mapping exclusively to the OBSERVATION table, while expediting the ETL process, reduces the value of the data to other researchers and hence, makes the value of the OMOP-CDM conversion questionable. In such a case, the analytics available may be confined to speciality analytics performed on the converted data itself - or identically formatted data – and will not be available in the full OHDSI tool stack. This issue will need to be dealt with at an organisational strategic level first, and second, at the level of any ICHOM standard set data presented for conversion to the OMOP-CDM format.

Does this match up with the expectations when the data dictionary itself was originally mapped to the OMOP-CDM?

⁴³ <https://ohdsi.github.io/TheBookOfOhdsi/>

⁴⁴ <https://forums.ohdsi.org/>